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Date: 2017-07-18	Deliverable D1.2	

TOYLABS

**D1.2 STAKEHOLDERS' REQUIREMENTS
IDENTIFICATION AND VALIDATION FRAMEWORK
DETERMINATION- V1 (M6)**

Document Owner:	NTUA
Contributors:	AIJU, FabLab Romania, FabLab Lecce, V-Cubes, JUEMA
Dissemination:	PUBLIC
Contributing to:	WP1 – Requirements Engineering and Validation Framework
Date:	2017-07-18
Revision:	0.9

Version history

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No.	Date	Notes and Comments
0.1	2017-03-03	Deliverable structure and ToC
0.2	2017-04-03	Final ToC and contributions defined
0.3	2017-05-03	Definition of ToyLabs' Requirement Gathering Methodology
0.4	2017-06-03	Inputs on Usage Scenarios and initial input on the Pilot Cases
0.5	2017-06-21	Elicitation of Requirements
0.6	2017-06-30	Inputs on the Validation Framework
0.7	2017-06-31	Conclusions, introductions and last updates
0.8	2017-07-05	Final version of D1.2 to be given for review
0.9	2017-07-10	Final version of D1.2 after review

Deliverable Peer Review Summary

ID	Comments	Addressed (✓) Answered (A)
1.		
2.		

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is part of ToyLabs WP1 – Requirement Engineering and Validation Framework. More specifically, it represents the work conducted for T1.3 - Stakeholders Requirements and High-level Usage Scenarios and T1.4 - ToyLabs Validation and Impact Measurement Framework. It is the second deliverable of the work package and it defines the Requirements 1) Identification and 2) Validation frameworks. According to the DoW in the grant agreement, D1.2 - Stakeholders' Requirements Identification and Validation Framework Determination has the following content:

“This deliverable will conduct certain high-level usage scenarios that will lead to the extraction of concrete requirements to be used for the methodology and the platform. Additionally, the framework for ToyLabs Validation and Impact Measurement will be initially described in the context of this deliverable.”

This deliverable is organised in two distinct parts. Part A – Stakeholders Requirement Identification, aims at generating the user requirements that will be used for the definition of the methodology and the design of the platform's features. In other words, Part A is the main outcome of T1.3 and will deliver the Requirement Gathering Methodology and the Pilots from which, more specific requirements will be collected.

Part B – Validation Framework Determination will work on the definition of criteria and indicators to measure impact and validate the success of the project's results. Being the main outcome of T1.4, it takes as input from Part A, the generalized requirements and defines the criteria that will validate them later in the project's lifecycle.

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PART A: STAKEHOLDERS REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

1 INTRODUCTION

The ToyLabs project aims at tackling the problems that small and medium sized industries (SMEs) are facing nowadays in Europe's toy manufacturing industry, to strengthen their position against global competitors. The ToyLabs platform will be built on the pillars of co-creation and open innovation aiming to strengthen the value network of an SME by bringing it closer to other key players of the industry such as FabLabs, Toy Safety/Environmental/Childhood Experts and end users. These stakeholders are expected to offer, apart from their services, valuable insights and feedback throughout the toy development process, validating the product at each stage. It is projected that the added value that SMEs will receive from the platform will improve their competitive position and show the road for increasing the competitiveness of the toy manufacturing industry in the EU.

The objective of WP1 is to investigate the current landscape of the toy industry under the scope of creativity and collaborative design. The process started from the exploration of the challenges it is facing and the identification of existing design and manufacturing processes, to afterwards define the impacts that the advanced technologies proposed by ToyLabs could have on the acceleration of the design and manufacturing process, as well as the product's commercial potential (D1.1 – Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition). WP1 will therefore lead to the elicitation of requirements, based on the user scenarios obtained through iterative interactions with the project's pilots for enhancing the creativity process and accelerating the time-to-market for new products (D1.2 - Stakeholders' Requirements Identification and Validation Framework Determination Part A). Emphasis will be given on the formulation of a solid framework for the validation and impact measurement of the project's results (D1.2 - Stakeholders' Requirements Identification and Validation Framework Determination Part B).

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

The main objectives of WP1 are the following:

- To investigate the project's innovation perspective and fully establish its approach;
- To explore the toy industry's business landscape; the opportunities and challenges under the project's scope;
- **To uptake user scenarios, capture and structure end-users' requirements as real-life examples;**
- **To manage and refine stakeholder requirements to prepare technical innovation;**

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- To prepare a framework for the effective validation of the project's results against the user requirements.

The first part of this deliverable reports on the activities in relation to task T1.3 – Stakeholder's Requirements and High-Level Usage Scenarios. It is important that the knowledge collected in the first deliverable D1.1 - EXPLORING PROGRESS AND INNOVATION IN TOYLABS TACKLED DOMAINS AND TOYLABS CONCEPT DEFINITION is broken down and analysed, so that the most basic requirements (drawn from the toy industry's biggest shortcomings) can be captured. Moreover, throughout the course of this task direct and frequent communication with all the partners of the consortium has been established, as their feedback is integral for evaluating and prioritising the requirements gathered.

The concrete objectives and expected results of D1.2 are the following:

- Identify all stakeholders involved in the ToyLabs platform
- Describe how value will return to every stakeholder through the enhanced collaboration
- Create high-level usage scenarios with the support of the pilot partners
- Extract requirements that correspond to the needs expressed by the pilot partners for improving collaboration and co-creation

Part A of D1.2 is structured in 4 chapters that provide the main information concerning Requirement Gathering such as the general methodology used, the Pilot's Requirement Identification phase and the specific requirements extracted from them.

Chapter 1 is the introduction to the document. It starts with the general description of ToyLabs, the objectives of WP1 in general and specifically the goals of T1.3. Moreover, it includes the structure of this document and the points of interaction between this deliverable and other Work Packages and tasks.

Chapter 2 is initially focused on identifying the different stakeholders of the ToyLabs platform. Additionally, it will describe the specific Requirement Gathering Methodology that will be used, explaining the specific steps of which it is comprised and the various procedures and tools used to draw information from the platform's stakeholders.

Chapter 3 is focused on the description of the pilots, introducing the companies involved in each trial, the current situation (as-is situation) and the main weaknesses and challenges to be addressed. Moreover, this chapter will try to uncover the user requirements of each pilot concerning the platform. These requirements will help uncover the added value that each pilot will receive after the ToyLabs services are implemented to each company's product development processes

Chapter 4 collects the main conclusions of the document.

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Finally, an annex will be included in order to provide the questionnaires' templates that were sent to toy manufacturers and members of the ToyLabs' consortium.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The structure of the deliverable is grouped into 2 major blocks; according to the objectives described in section 1.1 (see **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..1**):

Block A has the function to introduce the ToyLabs Requirements Identification approach and integrate the topic into the project context. Considering the innovative nature of the project and the characteristics of the Toy industry, the process of Requirements Engineering is presented. It consists of Chapters 1 and 2 and presents the approach in the scientific context.

Block B contains the user requirements, which are drawn from the pilots and usage scenarios of members and stakeholders of the consortium. Finally, the results are summarised and conclusions for the next steps are given.

Figure 1-1 - Structure of the Deliverable

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1.3 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS

The work presented in the present deliverable contains crucial information for all the following phases of the project. The general results obtained in this document will be connected and will contribute directly to WP2 – for the development of ToyLabs Methodological Framework and WP3 – for the specification of the requirements and characteristics of the ToyLabs platform.

Deliverable D1.2 takes input from D1.1 which provides the necessary information for the initial definition of ToyLab's requirements. It should be mentioned that these are abstract requirements, representing general needs in the Toy industry. Nevertheless, they are a valuable basis to start from, as they reveal the most common shortcomings of the EU toy industry today.

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2 TOYLABS REQUIREMENTS FRAMEWORK

2.1 STAKEHOLDERS' IDENTIFICATION & PLATFORM ROLES

The following table (table 1) contains the stakeholders that were identified in D1.1 – Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition. It must be mentioned that the previous deliverable identified the entirety of stakeholders that participate in a toy development process performed by an SME. However, some of the roles uncovered represent stakeholders that are not considered as individual entities in the ToyLabs' process and thus need to be identified and removed from the present analysis. As a result, the second table (table 2) of this chapter contains the ToyLabs platform stakeholders.

PROFILE	DESCRIPTION
Manufacturers	<p>A person, group, or company that owns or runs a manufacturing plant.</p> <p>Companies that are responsible of the whole process of creation a new toy, from its conceptualisation to delivering the toy to the shops</p>
Inventors	<p>People or companies that offer new toy ideas, concepts or designs, usually to manufacturers or distributors</p>
Designers	<p>People or companies that offer new toy ideas, concepts or designs, usually to manufacturers or distributors.</p> <p>Additionally, they can help evolve other people's concepts or ideas into designs</p>
Engineers	<p>People or companies that offer to help evolve conceptual designs to a more detailed stage with all the information needed for its mass production</p>
User experts	<p>Companies or persons that are experts and have the necessary infrastructure to test concepts, designs, prototypes and final products with final users (parents and children usually).</p> <p>The main variables that they use to analyse are: Level of appeal, usability and trend analysis.</p>

Marketers	People or companies who are experts in the promotion of toys. Their main activities are: advertising, social media management, product placement, sales and contact with distributors
Market and design researchers	People or companies who are experts in the detection of market and user needs. Their expertise is based on the transformation of these insights into new opportunities for the market
Safety experts	People or companies who are experts in analysing and applying all the safety standards that affect the toy industry
Suppliers	Companies that provide the necessary material, components and/ or machinery required by the manufacturers
Distributors	Companies that own toy stores or specific spaces for selling toys
Lawyers	A person whose profession is to represent clients in a court of law or to advise or act on their behalf in other legal matters.
FabLabs	A FabLab is an abbreviation from Fabrication Laboratory and it is defined as: a small-scale workshop offering (personal) digital fabrication.

Table 2-1 – Toy Industry Stakeholders

While the table above includes the different roles met in the Toy Industry and the types of experts offering their services on the basis of their expertise, in practise the majority of those stakeholders do not possess an individual position in the toy manufacturing landscape. For example, Designers, Engineers, Marketeers and Lawyers do not play an individual role in the toy creation process but they offer specific – and in most cases crucial – services directly to the rest of the identified stakeholders, (mostly to the Toy Manufacturers). Due to that and in order to build a solid methodological approach which will not be affected by the working relationships of those service providers with the manufacturing organisations, ToyLabs considers that these roles are actually covered by the Toy Manufacturer’s ecosystem. No matter if a Manufacturer has a design unit (which is the most common case) or uses external designers, for ToyLabs manufacturing design is considered to be implemented by the Manufacturer. In other words, the notion Manufacturer does represent a manufacturing

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organisation together with a number of experts offering their services either while belonging in the man force of the organisation, which is the most usual case, either while offering their services as external collaborators to the manufacturer.

Based on this assumption, the key roles considered in ToyLabs are four: manufacturers, user experts, safety experts and FabLabs. The rest of the stakeholders identified in D1.1 do participate in the process but through the organisations that they work for, so are not considered to have an individual role in the process.

As an additional role to those mentioned above, the ‘product owner’ notion must be mentioned at this point. As product owner in ToyLabs is considered the person/organisation that on the basis of a new idea sets up the process for creating a new toy. ToyLabs covers the case any member of the ToyLabs ecosystem having an idea for a new Toy to setup a toy creation process and through the Toylabs platform to create the necessary collaborations which can lead to the development of a new product. When the idea belongs to a manufacturer (which is the most usual case no matter if the manufacturer has initially developed or has acquired the idea from an inventor), then the manufacturer is considered as the product owner. On the other hand, when the original idea belongs to any other stakeholder, then this stakeholder keeps the product owner role which also is linked to having property rights on the product to be developed, no matter if for the development of the product a manufacturing company is involved. However in this case the property rights and whether they only belong to the product owner or partially to the product owner and partially to the manufacturer (or any other involved party) is an issue to be agreed between the collaborating parties and notarised in the contract between them.

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ROLE	DESCRIPTION	KEY TOYLABS ACTIVITIES
Toy Manufacturers	Organisations with manufacturing capabilities able to manage the whole process of creating a new toy, from its conceptualisation to delivering the toy to the shops.	Development of products Provider of mass manufacturing services
User experts / Childhood experts	Organisations or individual experts able to assess from an end-user or from a scientific point of view a new toy.	Provision of specialised feedback on new toys during their development Representation of potential end users, assessing the appeal and usability of the new product
Safety experts	People or companies who are experts in analysing and applying all the safety standards that affect the toy industry	Safety certification and consultancy of concepts, designs, prototypes and final products
FabLabs	Small-scale workshops offering (personal) digital fabrication.	Short series and prototype manufacturing Consultancy/ feedback regarding the product's design and engineering details

Table 2-2 - ToyLabs Main Identified Roles

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2.2 TOYLABS APPROACH FOR REQUIREMENTS ELICITATION

Nowadays, in the Requirement Elicitation processes there are two basic schools of thought, deriving from the two most popular product and software development approaches: Waterfall and Agile. The Waterfall approach describes requirements elicitation as “one-and-done” procedure, which once completed, it is costly to return to, later in the project’s run. In the waterfall model, once this phase is complete, the requirements are required to be fully developed and explained. In other words, once the requirements are defined, they can’t be changed later in the project’s lifecycle, unless with a significant cost. On the other hand, Agile focuses on the final product and breaks the development process down into smaller incremental builds, with some further requirement gathering in each cycle.

The requirements elicitation in ToyLabs is due to the nature of the project (and as agreed among the partners as most appropriate) a process that ideally shall combine the two popular models. In this framework an hybrid approach has been defined in order to guide the project through the requirements elicitation phase. Specifically, the project’s consortium has agreed that most of the requirements should be defined at the start of the project, before the platform’s development begins. That does not mean, though, that the entirety of the requirements will be fully defined in the beginning. In fact, the project, during its lifecycle, will have its requirements refined and enhanced, based on the feedback from the project’s stakeholders. The project aims to strike a balance between incremental and iterative methodologies, because, while most of the requirements must be set before the development begins, they must also be open to modification depending on the experience and feedback given by the end-users. In other words, this methodology incorporates agile characteristics, concerning the potential of changing the requirements mid-development, but in principle follows a waterfall-like approach with iterations, in the sense that the general requirements of each feature are sufficiently defined at the beginning of the project, even though there will be development circles (iteration) and additional elements/improvements can be introduced at the beginning of each iteration.

A main reason that a combined methodology is used, is that the requirement elicitation process involves many users and stakeholders, from which requirements are collected. However due to the different level of experience of the project stakeholders in implemented innovation projects and in providing detailed requirements from the beginning of the project, a pure waterfall model would not actually fit. The combined model developed allows gathering of the main requirements from all stakeholders early in the project’s lifecycle, but also keeps the requirements list open to modifications as the project stakeholders become involved and get a better understanding of the project itself. Of course, that means that no radical changes can be made after a certain point.

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2.2.1 General Description/Steps to be followed

This chapter, uses the general approach that was described in the previous chapter as its input, and will define a clearer methodology that will help with the Requirement Identification process from start to finish. The methodology that was constructed can be seen in Figure 2.1 and is divided into five distinct phases that will be described in greater detail in the following subchapters. It should be mentioned that the methodology only includes the phases that refer to the requirement capture and not the process of validation, which will be described in Part B of the present document. The figure, as well as the general methodology, was based on a Systems Engineering Guide in the site mitre.org¹. The MITRE Corporation is a not-for-profit company that operates multiple federally funded research and development centres occupying the role of a systems engineering company. The company has added numerous technical and organisational capabilities over the years serving both civil and military agencies. Finally, among the different requirement capturing techniques that exist today the following three were used:

1. **Questionnaires** are slightly informal but they are useful for gathering information from multiple stakeholders in remote locations, or stakeholders with minor input in the project's requirements. Thus, they were extremely helpful during the first stage of the requirement elicitation process when the general idea of what is needed to be done was still being formed.
2. **Interviews** are more formal and require more preparation, but are useful in uncovering a richer set of requirements in less time. As a result, the interviews that were conducted with the various stakeholders of the project's consortium helped uncover more detailed requirements during that stage of the requirement gathering process.
3. **Use Cases:** "A use case is a methodology used in system analysis to identify, clarify, and organise system requirements. The use case is made up of a set of possible sequences of interactions between systems and users in a particular environment and related to a particular goal... The use case should contain all system activities that have significance to the users. A use case can be thought of as a collection of possible scenarios related to a particular goal, indeed, the use case and goal are sometimes considered to be synonymous."² After analysing the information from the interview/questionnaires, a number of Use Case Scenarios were written about the different stakeholders of the platform, to describe how each partner will use the platform in a scenario. The scenarios were later reviewed by the relevant stakeholders who provided feedback and additional suggestions.

¹ <https://www.mitre.org/publications/systems-engineering-guide/se-lifecycle-building-blocks/requirements-engineering/eliciting-collecting-and-developing-requirements>

² <http://searchsoftwarequality.techtarget.com/definition/use-case>

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Figure 2-1 – Requirement Elicitation Methodology

2.2.1.1 Data Gathering

In the beginning of the Requirement Elicitation Methodology lies the stage of Data Gathering. The purpose of this phase is to collect industry related data to determine the state-of-the-art of toy manufacturing in Europe today. As shown in D1.1: Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition, Data Gathering was performed in two stages:

1. A desk research that used academic and non-academic sources to obtain useful knowledge concerning the following:
 - a. SOTA of collaborative development approaches in the manufacturing sector
 - b. SOTA of technologies offered by FabLabs in EU today
 - c. SOTA of design processes in toy manufacturing

Ultimately, the information collected during this phase was used to develop the questionnaire that was sent in the second stage of Data Gathering.

2. The second stage involved a first round of questionnaires that were sent to manufacturers who don't belong to the project's consortium. The desk research and the questionnaires had similar scopes and they were both included in the pursuit to be exhaustive in said research. Nevertheless, the questionnaires helped better perceive the problems that toy manufacturers face today and verify ToyLabs potential impact in solving these problems.

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2.2.1.2 Initial Requirement Gathering

The second phase, Initial Requirement Gathering, involved a second round of more personalised questionnaires that were sent to members of the ToyLabs' consortium (Toy Manufacturers, FabLabs, and Safety Experts). The different consortium groups, being more invested in the results of the project, provided invaluable insights to the first round's data. While the first round helped in the gathering of general information, it was thought that a second survey was necessary to shape this information into what would eventually be the High-Level User Requirements of the ToyLabs platform. Given that the questionnaires were different depending on the consortium member, the project's partners managed to identify the general demands of each group of users that is going to use the platform.

2.2.1.3 Requirement Details Gathering

This phase included interviews with the consortium members (Toy Manufacturers, FabLabs, Safety Experts and End-Users) to create the detailed requirements. This stage is crucial to the overall process because the requirements defined in it, will be later translated into the features that will guide the platform's development. In other words, this phase will help us define the core features of the platform and, even though they are open to modification during the other iterations of requirement gathering, they cannot be completely redefined because, due to the short duration of the project, it would be a setback to the project's schedule.

2.2.1.4 Prioritize Requirements

This phase is responsible for defining the criteria with which, the features described during the last phase, will be prioritised. During the interview phase, stakeholders were asked at the end of the procedure to say which of the requirements that they proposed, they consider as being the most important. Later these requirements were turned into user stories that were rated by the consortium partners. Based on the stakeholders' feedback and the average rating of the user stories, the features are divided into the following categories:

1. **Essential Features** are the core features of the platform. They are integral to the project's scope and should be implemented before anything else. As shown in Figure 2.1 these features are the input of the first development iteration.
2. **Important features** are features that are not central to the platform's core functionality, but are crucial at enabling the project's methodology to be substantiated. These features require the essential features to be implemented to a certain functional degree, before they are themselves developed. Consequently, they are going to be implemented during the second iteration.
3. **Tentative features** are the added value features that aim at augmenting the functionality of certain aspects or other features of the platform, based on the overall methodological approach of the project. These are not vital for the

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platform's operation, but instead extend the scope and capabilities of the supported workflows, which means that they can be implemented last in this sequence.

2.2.1.5 Requirement Gathering Iterations

Following the Agile method, the development of the platform will be divided into three iterations that will use the features that were defined during the Requirement Details Gathering stage as input. The first phase of each iteration will be devoted to an additional cycle of requirement gathering. These cycles will be less intense and they will focus more on modifying existing features, based on new ideas and information, rather than defining new ones. Thus, it stands to reason that during the iterations nearing the end of the development phase, the modifications will be more specific and less time-consuming to implement, given that as time passes the pool of information becomes larger, but stricter time restraints apply.

2.2.2 Stakeholders' Requirements Collection Approach

In this chapter, the methods and techniques that were used to identify the platform requirements from both toy industry representatives and from the consortium's partners will be described. Specifically, a mix of interviews and questionnaires were used and the answers received were integral in identifying the high-level requirements of the ToyLabs platform. The questionnaires that were sent to both toy industry representatives as well as members of the consortium are in Annex I.

2.2.2.1 Input from toy industry representatives

The input from toy industry representatives was received via questionnaires that were sent during the first stages of the project. The information gathered during this phase helped identify the most common processes, materials used, collaboration relationships etc. in the toy industry. This information was a great addition to the desk research and will be used during certain stages of the platform's development.

2.2.2.2 Partners-specific Input

For members of the consortium (manufacturers, FabLabs, experts), at first a questionnaire was sent. The purpose of that questionnaire was to identify current roles and procedures in the toy industry to identify at which exact points the ToyLabs platform can add value to the toy development process. Industrial partners (manufacturers) were asked to describe their usual new product development process, their collaborations with other stakeholders, the most common problems that they face etc. Non-industrial partners (FabLabs, experts) were asked to describe among others, the services that they offer to manufacturers at each stage of new product development.

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The answers given in the questionnaires were studied and used to create the questions for the interviews that took place shortly after. In other words, the questionnaires helped identify the most important (according to ToyLabs' partners) services the platform should provide, prioritise future work, and propose features that were not originally included in the platform's initial scope, but proved to be useful additions.

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3 USER'S REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

This chapter is responsible for describing the platform's stakeholders that will participate in the Pilot phase, realise the challenges that each one is facing, and use these challenges to uncover each partner's requirements for the ToyLabs platform. The preparation for this task included a series of questionnaires and interviews with the stakeholders, as well as an open discussion that took place during the project's first plenary meeting and all the tele-conferences until then. The pilots include two manufacturing companies, V-Cubes and JUEMA. Additionally, two FabLabs (FabLab Romania and FabLab Lecce) and AIJU, an organisation that performs safety assessment tests in toys, participate in the project from the beginning and will be presented in this chapter to explain the added value that they are expected to offer to the manufacturers. For each pilot, a general description of the organisation will be given, as well as the current pilot's situation and its usual procedure during the development of a new product from the phase of Immersion & Concept Definition until the Commercialisation of the final product. Moreover, the problems that each pilot is facing are described, and these will be that will lead to the requirements that each organisation expects from the platform. Later in this chapter, the information gathered will be used to elicit several high-level use case scenarios. Finally, taking advantage of all the knowledge gathered in the above steps the general user requirements will be identified.

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3.1 MECHANICAL PUZZLE TOYS PILOT (V-CUBES)

3.1.1 Description and pre-elicitation phase

Verdes Innovations S.A. was founded in 2008 and is in Korinthos of Southern Greece. Verdes Innovations S.A. designs and produces its products in Greece and promotes them via a well-established and fast-growing network of distributors in more than 30 countries. Moreover V-Cubes products have reached 112 countries via the web and its best-selling markets are Spain, USA, Canada, Switzerland, France, Germany, Netherlands and Greece amongst others.

The company manufactures so far more than 100 SKUs categorized in 3 major **Brands**.

The V-CUBE™ worldwide patented products. They are a uniquely designed and constructed series of 3D rotational cubes that managed to break a worldwide monopoly for the best-selling puzzle in history. They are classified in 3 different sub-categories: The V-Classics, The V-Collections and the “Create Your Cube” products.

The V-Sphere™ patented product, a new 3D sliding spherical puzzle.

The Labours of Hercules, an innovative series of 2D pattern puzzles.

V-Cubes products are addressed to kids and parents, students and teachers, professionals and artists, tourists and museum lovers, companies and licensees. Their unique features allow literally everyone to enjoy them and enhance the puzzle solving experience, while offering both challenging and stepping levels of difficulty.

V-Cubes’ **vision** is to provide to people worldwide an opportunity to extend their capabilities and develop pluralistic creative skills using innovative and educational series of puzzles. In that scope, it is important for the company to stay competitive and innovative in today’s fast-moving business climate, while also maintaining the high-quality standards and creativity that made the company stand out from its competition.

3.1.2 Current Pilot’s Situation/Scenario

VERDES Innovations S.A. consists of an R&D division, a production division, a marketing-sales division, a logistic division and a customer support division, all of which strive to provide the best quality control and customer service support possible. All contemporary and safety standards are used to accommodate its global customers.

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3.1.2.1 Business Processes and Tasks for new product/toy development/manufacturing

#	Process	Description (with its main assets)
A0	Immersion & Concept Definition	V-Cubes has an idea for a new product
A1	Feasibility Study	V-Cubes executes a feasibility study in collaboration with various experts to find out if a new idea has commercial potential
A1.1	Finding experts	V-Cubes searches for toy experts, distributors, toy safety experts etc.
A1.2	Examine Basic and Unique Characteristics of the Idea	V-Cubes checks how innovative and appealing the idea is by consulting toy experts and distributors. Moreover, V-Cubes examines if it can protect the idea.
A1.3	Set the main targeted goals	Select the countries in which the product will be sold, the targeted groups etc.
A1.4	Analyse relevant products	Examine relevant products in terms of costs and sales on the same target
A1.5	Calculate investments	Rough calculation of the investments needed to reach the competition level in terms of production, marketing and intellectual property expenses
A1.6	Project sales	V-Cubes calculates the potential sales of the idea
A1.7	Evaluation	V-Cubes values the feasibility and checks the sustainability of the idea
A1.8	Production & Marketing plan	V-Cubes designs a basic production and marketing plan

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A2	Finding & Securing the Capital	V-Cubes has to find capital in one of the following ways: own resources, bank credit, governmental or EU funding, angel investors, equity or joint ventures partners
A3	Execute Intellectual Property Plan	*This step can last a lot of time. That means that V-Cubes may proceed to the next step before finalizing this one
A3.1	Decide the Plan	V-Cubes decides with the help of the experts the intellectual plan
A3.2	Apply for the plan	When the plan is ready, V-Cubes makes an application to the relevant organisations to accept the plan
A3.3	Monitor the progress	V-Cubes monitors the application's progress until it is complete, solving potential problems as they come
A3.4	Register and renew the rights	If the application is successful, then V-Cubes must perform all necessary actions to keep the registration alive
A4	Product Development	Includes every action relevant to the development of the final toy
A4.1	Re-check Production & Marketing Plan	Re-Validation of the production & marketing plans before the toy development begins
A4.2	Select basic Raw Material	Selection of the material of construction for the final product
A4.3	Select Size & Dimensional Figures	Selection of the final product's dimensions. At this stage collaboration with the external experts that will construct the prototype is needed in order to harmonise the prototype with the production goals

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A4.4	Decide the Finishing	Selection of techniques and materials to finish the product (product finishing has to do with coating the product's surface with specific materials in order to make it smoother)
A4.5	Design & Simulate in PC	Design the product with the help of computer tools. This step takes place after the details about the toy's construction have been decided (steps A4.2-A4.4)
A4.6	Prototype	Construction of the prototype (usually performed by external experts such as printing houses and CAD-CAM labs)
A4.7	Test the Prototype	V-Cubes tests the pre-production item by sending it to beta testers (experienced clients) and big customers (mainly for general feeling of the toy)
A4.8	Develop Packaging	Develop the packaging for the toy (this step is delayed in order to account for potential changes in the product's dimensions)
A4.9	Safety Test	Testing of the toy by safety experts to ensure that it follows the necessary safety standards

Table 3-1 - V-Cubes Business Processes

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Figure 3-1 - V-Cubes Product Development Procedure

3.1.2.2 Identified Challenges

Challenge 1:

One of the main problems that V-Cubes is facing today is the harmonisation and the development of the prototype with the production and marketing goals. Given that prototyping and safety checks are handled by external collaborators, the company lacks the communication and visualisation tools that would allow them to participate and receive direct feedback from their partners.

Challenge 2:

Another problem that V-Cubes faces is the selection of the dimensions of a given product as well as the selection of the finishing. These problems may seem trivial, but if not handled correctly, can lead to problems during the prototyping phase.

Challenge 3:

Realising the potential of a new idea/concept: Given that V-Cubes is concerned with the construction of 3D puzzle toys that have a very specific target audience, sometimes it is difficult to know beforehand if a new idea is going to be well received

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by the consumers, especially if the company is not willing to spend thousands of dollars for market reports and analyses.

Challenge 4:

Finding the right partners for the right job: Given that the development of a new toy is a complex procedure that requires the attention and collaboration of many parties, sometimes it is hard to find the right partners or even find a new reliable partner in case a primary collaborator is unavailable.

Challenge 5:

The company uses several different tools and lacks a platform that will include the sum of the systems and databases needed for the development of a new toy.

3.1.3 Objectives and Derived User Requirements

Req #	Requirement	ToyLabs Proposed Solution	Problem #
1	Improved communication among the collaborating parties of a new product development process	Communication is one of the main pillars of the ToyLabs platform and its added value is mainly based on cooperation between partners	1
2	Better organisational tools to deal with lack of harmonization between phases.	The phases of product development will be clearly defined in the platform's workspace so that the manufacturer can better organise the process.	1
3	Cooperation with organisations that can help during the design of a new product and the definition of its parameters	Usage of the partner matching module to find relevant collaborators	2
4	Implementation of a tool that can accommodate the company's needs to uncover public opinion	Usage of the Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component to identify public opinion about an idea/concept/product	3

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	before the release of a product		
5	Implementation of a database that contains different stakeholders of the toy industry and a tool to search for the right ones	The platform's database will include every stakeholder that participates in the platform and with the help of the partner matching module the manufacturer can find the right one.	4
6	Implementation of the tools needed for the different stages of product development into a single workspace for better organisation	ToyLabs will include all the vital services that a manufacturer needs during the development of a new toy	5

Table 3-2 - V-Cubes Derived Requirements

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3.2 DOLLS & ACCESSORIES PILOT (JUEMA)

3.2.1 Description and pre-elicitation phase

INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA S.L. is dedicated to the creation, manufacturing and marketing, for others, of all kinds of dolls and toys, vinyl and cloth. It maintains a quality management system based on the UNE-EN-ISO9001: 2015, supported by the following principles:

- **INNOVATION, INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA S.L.** is committed to innovation on the original products to meet the demands of its customers.
- **DESIGN AND CREATION**, design is a distinguishing feature of JUEMA's products, and it is important for them to create designs that have market acceptance.
- **COMPLIANCE WITH LEGAL PRODUCT REQUIREMENTS**, the product is manufactured under quality controls required by the regulations of the countries of origin of the customers.
- **CUSTOMER SERVICE**, the staff of the organisation is committed to the customers, personally attending their needs and requirements, since the moment they contact JUEMA, to comply the requests properly.
- **DELIVERY**, for INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA S.L it is very important to deliver the customer's orders on time without delays that may affect them.
- **QUALITY**, the quality management system implemented at INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA S.L. allows control over the quality requirements demanded by customers, committing to compliance and continuous improvement of the effectiveness of the quality management system.

3.2.2 Current Pilot's Situation/Scenario

JUEMA is a company that handles manufacturing requests from clients who provide their designs but do not have the mass manufacturing capabilities or the skilled workforce needed to create vinyl/cloth dolls/toys. In other words, their business processes do not include the stages of Immersion & Concept Definition, Design and Commercialisation given that they do not have ownership of the concept or the final product. As a result, JUEMA mainly handles the construction of the moulds and prototypes and the mass manufacturing of the final product.

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3.2.2.1 Business Processes and Tasks for new product/toy development/manufacturing

#	Process	Description (with its main assets)
A1	Development of Sculpture for Production	The client contacts JUEMA for its own already developed design
A1.1	Design Review	JUEMA reviews the design from a technical point of view and advises the client on how to improve it in order to avoid problems during manufacturing
A1.2	Prototype	Prototype in wax sculpture to proceed with mould making
A2	Pre-Production	Task related with the tasks that need to be completed before the product is ready for mass production
A2.1	Making Master & Production Moulds	Construction of the moulds that will be used to shape the dolls
A2.2	Rotomoulding Oven	Tests of the already created moulds. Prototype for vinyl parts. Usually a client contacts the safety experts but we can include it in our services and contact the laboratories for tests and assessments.
A3	Production	Step by step development of the final product
A3.1	Hair Rooting & Eyes Implanting	Development of the doll's head
A3.2	Dolls Decoration	Decoration of the doll such as shaping, colouring etc.
A3.3	Dressmaking	Production of the doll's dress

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A3.4	Stuffing of soft-bodied Dolls	Stuffing of the final doll (the material depends on the toy itself as well as who the toy is being made for)
A3.5	Dolls & Toys Assembling	Assembling of the final doll from the different parts that were constructed during this phase
A3.6	Development/ Manufacturing of Packaging	Before manufacturing the packaging JUEMA receives instructions from the client concerning the style/ graphic design and indications about the age grade

Table 3-3 - JUEMA's Business Processes

3.2.2.2 Identified Challenges

Most of JUEMA's problems arise from the fact that a lot of their clients are new to the toy industry and thus often require impossible services. A list of the most common problems that JUEMA is facing today is the following:

Challenge 1:

A client isn't informed very well about the doll manufacturing process and is new in this industry. The problem arises when the client requires impossible designs and JUEMA's usual solution of explaining step by step what can and cannot be done oftentimes leads to the client's disappointment.

Challenge 2:

Given that JUEMA only deals with the phases of prototyping and production, it falls to the client to collect feedback regarding the safety/environmental assessment of the toy. Oftentimes, the product owner does not possess the necessary channels to find the stakeholders that can handle the above processes.

Challenge 3:

Finding suppliers for some components like fabrics, shoes or eyes. Most of the Spanish doll industry has disappeared or "recycled" for other purposes and as a result it is very complicated to find fabrics that would comply with general toy safety requirements. Consequently, JUEMA is constantly trying to find new suppliers even if that means buying some materials in Asia.

Challenge 4:

Lack of dress making workshops: this problem stems from the same source as Problem 2, which is that professionals of the toy industry terminate their services. As a result, these past two years JUEMA has tried to work with several new workshops but was left disappointed by most of them.

3.2.3 Objectives and Derived User Requirements

Req #	Requirement	ToyLabs Proposed Solution	Problem #
1	Find the correct experts that will give the early feedback needed by the client for him to have more realistic demands	Usage of the partner matching module from the early stages of product development to identify the necessary collaborations throughout a development cycle	1,2
2	JUEMA would ideally want to be able to skip one or more phases of product development in the ToyLabs platform given that they only handle prototyping and manufacturing.	The platform will offer the ability to skip one or more phases of product development according to the needs of the user	2
3	Finding the right stakeholders that can reliably handle the handful of manufacturing tasks that JUEMA does not do in their factory.	Apart from the partner matching module the platform will include a rating system so that manufacturers will know which of their choices was deemed to be more reliable by other manufacturers	3,4

Table 3-4 - JUEMA's Derived Requirements

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3.3 NON-INDUSTRIAL TOYLABS STAKEHOLDERS

3.3.1 FabLab Romania & FabLab Lecce

3.3.1.1 General Description

FabLab Romania is a creative space based in Bucharest with a clear practical side; A FabLab aims to provide the environment, skills, advanced materials and technology to make things quickly anywhere in the world and to make this available on a local basis to entrepreneurs, students, artists, small businesses and more. FabLab Romania's project covers a variety of fields but mainly circles around manufacturing, product design and model making and they almost always imply a final project of a physical nature (an object, a model, a trophy etc.).

Start Smart srl (FabLab Lecce) is a company that was founded in 2014 and provides innovative and high value technological services. It is focused on Consulting, Design, Modelling, Prototyping and Small Series Production, using Digital Technologies (such as Additive Manufacturing and Virtual Reality). Furthermore, it provides services of R&D, Education, Training and Events Planning focused on exponential growing technologies and their using.

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Business Processes and Tasks related to the Pilots' scenarios

#	Process	Description
1	Design	Give technical feedback regarding a design so that the transition of the design into the prototype will be smoother and without problems
2	Prototyping	FabLabs have the technical capabilities to build prototypes more efficiently than manufacturers who are mostly focused on mass manufacturing
3	Safety Assessment	FabLabs have the experience to give feedback regarding safety issues of a design or prototype but not regarding safety standards (for that a safety expert is needed)

Table 3-5 - FabLabs' Business Processes in Toy Development

It can be concluded that FabLabs are an important asset for the ToyLabs platform, providing key services during the design/prototyping phases but also participating throughout the whole procedure at the manufacturer's request. What FabLabs earn by participating in the platform is expanding their customer network and having a space in which they can find more possible collaboration opportunities that go beyond their usual geographical barriers.

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3.3.2 Toy Safety Experts (AIJU)

3.3.2.1 General Description

AIJU is a private non-profit organisation aiming to boost research development and technological innovation within toys, children's products and leisure traditional manufacturing industries, as well as their auxiliary industries, thus making it possible the achievement of a constant competitiveness increase and product quality improvement.

It was founded in 1985 and located in Ibi, the Spanish geographic centre for the toy manufacturing where most of the toy manufacturers are gathered, to allow them to have access and knowledge to new technologies.

AIJU has near 450 associated services distributed in two main blocks, children products manufacturers and industrial auxiliary. Other articles' manufacturers include playground, infant feeding & promotions, among others while auxiliary industry includes moulds manufacturers, raw material suppliers, coatings, graphic arts and metal processing. More than 70% of current toy manufacturers are associated, which represent more than 77% of the sector turnover.

AIJU's Laboratory has been involved in the field of child safety since 1986, where the organisation got a National Accreditation from ENAC on Toys Safety. AIJU has additional accreditations regarding food contact materials, child care articles, inspection activities and playgrounds and is an accredited entity in the register of training centres and entities of vocational training for employment.

AIJU is an active member of the Committees that set the standards for child products' (toys -CEN/TC 52, childcare articles- CEN/TC 252 and playgrounds – CEN/TC136/SC1, CENELEC/TC61 WG7 electrical toys and other consumer articles) as well as ISO/TC 261 "Additive Manufacturing".

The organisation is a notified body in the European Union in accordance with Directive 2009/48/CE to carry out EC type examination for toys. The ENAC accreditation involves safety tests according to European standards (EN 71 and EN 62115).

AIJU is accredited as a third-party laboratory in US. It is recognized by the CPSC (Consumer Product Safety Commission) for testing according to American standards, and performs the tests according to other international regulations (ISO, IEC, CPSIA, Canadian SOR, etc.) and other standards related to childcare articles, playgrounds and bicycles.

AIJU also gives advice on the preparation of the technical documentation required by the Directive for the CE safety mark, RoHS, REACH, CMR substances,

etc. AIJU carries out an important collaboration with the Spanish Authorities on Market Surveillance and Customs as testing laboratory.

AIJU also has a user expert department. The aim of the "Child Consumer and Leisure for All" department is to carry out studies related to children and therapeutic leisure for all (young, old or handicapped people), specialising in research and validation with end-users at national, European and international level. This area also conducts research based on information obtained from play centres, schools, consumer panels and expert panels, which collaborate with AIJU.

3.3.2.2 Business Processes and Tasks related to the Pilots' scenarios

#	Process	Description
1	Immersion & Concept Definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety Hazards And Design Reliability Evaluation • Studies with consumer/user expert etc.
2	Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Safety Hazards and Design Reliability Assessment</u> • <u>Initial Design Requirements</u> • <u>Design Validation</u> • Studies with consumer/user expert etc.
3	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Safety Hazards and Prototype Reliability Assessment</u> • <u>Advice in Labelling</u> • <u>Electronics for Process Control</u>
4	Pre-Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Safety Testing</u> • <u>Identification and Testing of Material</u>
5	Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety Tests • Studies with consumer/user expert etc.
6	Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety in Use

Table 3-6 - AIJU's Business Processes in Toy Development

AIJU's main income comes from product testing throughout the whole cycle of product development, from the Immersion & Concept Definition stage to the latter stages when the product is in its final form. However, they can also provide consulting

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services as far as a design, prototype or final product is concerned even though, currently, they lack the platform and tools to provide such services. As a result, through the ToyLabs platform, AIJU stands to expand their range of services while at the same time widening their customer network by exploring new job opportunities.

3.4 DERIVED HIGH-LEVEL USAGE SCENARIOS

3.4.1 Toy Manufacturer's Perspective

In the present section, two scenarios are presented showing how ToyLabs will support a Toy Manufacturer during the product development process. It should be mentioned that the toy manufacturer does not have to be the actual product owner, i.e. the one that has an idea for a new product (even though that will be the usual case). In fact, any member of the platform, whether that is a childhood expert, an end-user, a FabLab or someone else can have an idea for a new product. In that case the person/organisation that has the idea for a new toy uses the partner matching module to search for a manufacturer that can help him develop his idea into a product. After the user finds a manufacturer that can fulfil his needs, the two parties sign an agreement that irons out the details for the procedure and the final product. In this case, the process described in the next sub-chapters is fulfilled by the manufacturer under the permission of the main product owner, who monitors the process without however having the responsibility to manage it in the platform.

3.4.1.1 Toy Manufacturer Usage Scenario #1

A toy manufacturer wants to create a new product based on an existing one that he already has on the market. He feels like that product could be improved with some fresh ideas and an enhanced/ updated version to be released. He has been informed about ToyLabs from the project's personalized campaigns in social media and decided to give it a try and see if the platform can help him realize his idea throughout the whole process of product development as advertised. Thus, he decides to visit the platform's URL to test ToyLabs' services. The first thing he must do is sign up. He fills in the information needed to sign up (company name, domain, available technologies etc.) and after getting accepted in the platform (approved by the platform administrator as a manufacturer) he is ready to start. After signing up, he finds himself at the platform's starting dashboard, where he would normally see his active/ ongoing projects and the phase/ stage of product development that each of these products is at. If he wants to start a new project, there is also an option in the starting dashboard for that. Given that this is the manufacturer's first project on the platform he selects this option. On the following screen, he can see the different stages of new product development and the additional modules (sentiment analysis, partner matching, augmented reality) that can be used (depending on the stage).

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The first stage of every new product development process is the stage of Immersion & Concept Definition. In this case, the manufacturer has a general idea about what he wants his new product to be but he wants to learn what people are saying about his previous product on which the new one will be based. As a result, he uses ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component to get feedback on his old product in question and learn what his customers are saying about it (pros, cons, things to improve etc.). This procedure will make him realize what problems consumers had with the existing product and design the new product to be developed accordingly. Therefore, to begin with he selects the social media/web sources that he is interested in searching. After that, he must configure the ToyLabs platform to search for specific terms related to the existing product. The ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component also gives him the possibility to enable or disable the "influencers' mode" (on social media, influencers are people with influencing power in a broad web audience on a specific topic). On that case, since the manufacturer wants to design a product based on an existing one, he decides to disable the "influencers' mode" since he is mostly interested in his customers' opinion as a whole, instead of what influential people are saying about his existing product. After all these are set, he initializes the Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component and he receives the following results ("product w" is his existing product):

- 70% of comments are positive about "product w".
- When talking about "product w" they are also talking about x, y, z words.
- On January, there was a 30% increase in the times "product w" was referenced.
- When talking about "product w" 25% of people were dissatisfied with features a, b and 15% were surprised that the toy lacked feature c.

Now, the manufacturer is able to build on these useful insights gained and have a greater appreciation of what his customers might enjoy or even areas of improvement for his existing product.

After the market analysis is complete, the manufacturer has a clearer idea of what his future product should be. Consequently, he enters the design phase, creates an initial design and searches for FabLabs to support the process. Moreover, he designs the packaging for the final product which is also crucial for cost and safety issues. He knew in advance that this task is performed with the help of ToyLabs' partner matching component in one of the following two ways. The first way allows him to make an Open Request for a FabLab in which case, he will have to provide the description of his design such as technical/ material requirements, time/ cost requirements and safety/environmental requirements. Finally, he can describe additional customization parameters e.g. need for localized versions. In that case, FabLabs that are active on the partner matching module (or the Open Call section) and can handle the manufacturer's demands are going to send responses to the manufacturer applying for the job. To protect the manufacturer from copyright infringement concerning his idea, stakeholders that enter the Open Call section will be

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required to sign a confidentiality agreement that will ensure that no information about the design/idea of the manufacturer is leaked. That, combined with the agreement that every stakeholder will have to agree to when he signs up to the platform will ensure that there will be no information leakage outside of the platform. Finally, the manufacturer can select the most suitable FabLab based on each FabLab's profile and how it suits his needs. The second way allows him to enter ToyLabs Partner Matching Component and search himself for suitable FabLabs. In that case the platform enables the manufacturer to filter the results based on the FabLab's capabilities, skills, available equipment and materials used as well as location and qualifications/certifications. In this case, the manufacturer decides to describe what he needs, make an Open Call and see how many offers he will get.

At this point, the manufacturer has the choice to perform a product development cost/feasibility study with the help of the stakeholders that he has identified up to this point and the ToyLabs platform. That means that the manufacturer can perform an analysis that will let him know the ballpark cost for the development of a new product. It must be mentioned that this is an optional step. In fact, the manufacturer has the right to skip not only this one but more of the basic steps of the procedure based on his needs/preferences. In other words, it is not mandatory for a platform user to follow the procedure by the book as the platform is designed to be flexible.

Getting back to the feasibility study, the FabLabs can provide prices for their consulting and prototyping services, including the focus groups and the possibility of localization in latter stages. Moreover, if the manufacturer has already identified the safety/environmental experts that he will need in latter stages he will know the price of their services as well. Being new in the platform, the manufacturer decides to take advantage of this feature and compare the result with his usual cost for developing a new product. After communicating with his potential collaborators, he sees that the whole procedure will cost less than his usual one. Glad of the news he gets back to the partner matching stage.

After some time, he has received several offers from FabLabs that want to undertake the construction of his prototype. He enters each of the FabLabs profiles, decides on the most suitable and makes a request for collaboration. The FabLab accepts and now the two partners sign a confidentiality agreement in order to safeguard the manufacturer's intellectual property and agree upon the terms of their collaboration (cost, time for prototype completion, quality and materials used). After the terms are agreed and all the legal documents exchanged, the manufacturer consider the FabLab to be a trusted member of the development process that can give recommendations on technical issues and related comments on the design. In other words, this is the point at which the manufacturer shares the whole design and toy idea. At this point, it must be mentioned that the whole procedure will be closed and not visible to members of the platform that the manufacturer does not cooperate with currently, unless he decides to do so in specific steps in which he might need more open feedback.

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When the technical characteristics of the design are finalised with the help of the FabLabs, the manufacturer contacts safety/environmental experts for another round of feedback concerning both the product and the packaging. To contact safety/environmental experts, the manufacturer will once more use the Partner Matching module. As in the previous case when the manufacturer was searching for FabLabs, he can either make an Open Request or enter the ToyLabs' Partner Matching component himself. He decides to follow the same procedure as before being happy with the previous results. Moreover, still being new to the platform, he does not feel confident enough to use the Partner Matching module himself. Just like in the previous stage, he fills in information about his product and the services he is looking for. After a while, several Safety Experts contacts him requesting the contract and much like before, the manufacturer scrolls through each of the profiles and decides on which FabLab can fulfil his needs best.

At this point, the safety experts provide safety recommendations based on their experience and international standards so that the toy's design can be considered safe for the age group that it is intended for. Moreover, environmental experts provide recommendations related to the toy's and the package's environmental implications that can affect, among others, the construction material and the manufacturing process.

After the above stages are complete, the design is finalised and the manufacturer requests from FabLabs to proceed with prototyping based on the materials and processes that were agreed upon during the previous stages. The FabLabs create the prototypes, which they then enhance with AR through ToyLabs Augmented Reality Engine. That means that after the prototype's construction, the manufacturer can immediately have a realistic 3D design of his product which he can then send to Safety/Environmental experts and end-users for a second round of feedback. At this stage, the Safety Experts pre-certify the prototype or provide further recommendations for ensuring compliance with EU standards. Moreover, the environmental experts provide technical advice and manufacturer-specific recommendations regarding the reduction of the environmental impact of producing the toys. After some back and forth communication between the manufacturer and the experts the prototype is approved.

At this point, the manufacturer (with the help of the platform) may use the platform for populating focus groups so that end-users can interact with the toy prototype and give advice about improving it. The actual focus group meetings may be organized (depending on the location) either by the Fablab(s), the Safety Expert or the Manufacturer himself. Even though the recommendations may not be very specific in some cases, this is still a very important stage because it reveals the first impression of the potential end users of the product. Moreover, the need for localized versions of the toy can be identified here towards the direction of having greater potential in the local markets.

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Then, the manufacturer uses the partner matching module again to contact Childhood Experts that are members of the ToyLabs consortium for feedback. The partner matching module once more, allows the manufacturer to filter the results based on information such as qualification, expertise, skills and location. The last two phases of feedback (focus groups, Childhood experts) require the manufacturer to provide some incentives to those groups to ensure their participation. The manufacturer decides to offer free samples of the toy when it is finished to people with an active role who will provide recommendations about his product. Moreover, he decides to offer coupons for small discounts on his products just for participating in the focus groups. Finally, the platform includes a rating system that encourages experts and end-users to participate in the process and perform well. After describing his product one more and using the Partner Matching module he receives some responses. He rejects a few that have mediocre ratings and decides on those who can satisfy his needs the best.

At this point, the manufacturer has the final prototype and he is ready to proceed with the latter stages of product development (production, commercialisation). Having the prototype, the manufacturer now proceeds to a sample production (pre-series production) of the final product that is made of the actual material that will be used later for mass-production. When the batch is ready, the manufacturer, collaborating with the FabLabs, organizes focus groups consisting of childhood experts for another round of feedback, concerning the operational assessment of the product. When this phase is complete, then another round of Safety/Environmental Assessment (on the final product and the localized versions, not the prototype) takes place. Finally, the manufacturer with the help of childhood experts organizes focus groups with end-users (i.e. children), who provide feedback that can be used later during the product's commercialisation. What is noteworthy during the last phase of the product development process is that feedback is gathered (with the help of the ToyLabs platform) even after the product is ready for market. The manufacturer is very glad of this service because he feels that this feedback can lead to improvements on the product and the commercialisation strategy. Finally, when the procedure is complete and the product is ready, the platform will include a static page for commercialization purposes, in which the manufacturer can advertise his product and provide a link for his website.

3.4.1.2 Toy Manufacturer Usage Scenario #2

A toy manufacturer that is a member of the ToyLabs platform has an idea about a new original product. He has used the platform in the past for the same purpose and the results left him very satisfied. Thus, he decides to follow the same process again. He logs into the platform and starts working immediately. At the starting dashboard, he can see his ongoing projects and the stage of product development that each project is at. However, he selects the option that allows him to create a new project. On the following screen, he sees the phases of new product development in order and the platform's modules that can be used in each phase.

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The first stage of every new product development process is the stage of Immersion & Concept Definition. In this case, the manufacturer wants to learn about how people are currently responding to products of similar ranges. As a result, he enters ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component to learn what toy consumers are saying about comparable products. This procedure will help him realize if his idea has the potential to be successful. To begin with he selects the social media/web sources that he is interested in searching. He configures the ToyLabs platform to search for the specific words that he has chosen (e.g. puzzle games or a general description of his idea) in the various selected sources. Finally, he decides to enable "influencers' mode" because he feels that in this case influencers can "manipulate" their followers. At this point he initializes the module and receives the following results (w is the name of the range of products that his idea falls in e.g. puzzle games, action figures etc.).

- 15% of comments are negative about "w".
- When talking about "w" they are also talking about x, y, z words.
- From April to June there was a 10% increase in the times "w" was referenced.

Using that kind of information, the manufacturer realizes that his idea has the potential to be successful, so he decides to proceed to the next steps of the development process.

After the market analysis is complete, the manufacturer has a clearer idea of what his future product should be. Consequently, he creates an initial design (for both the product and the packaging) and searches for FabLabs to support the process. Having used the Open Call section in a previous project he decides that in this case his approach will be more hands-on. As a result, he decides to enter the partner matching module himself. He enters suitable search terms in the filters concerning the services that he wants the FabLab to be able to satisfy.

At this point (before construction of the prototype), the manufacturer must decide whether he will do a product development feasibility analysis or not. Nonetheless, he decides that he wants the procedure to be as quick as possible. Furthermore, he has used the platform before and has a lot of experience in a product's development process. Consequently, he decides to omit this phase and proceed to completing the current phase. As was already mentioned, this step as well as the rest of the stages of product development may be skipped by the manufacturer if he so desires.

After filling in the filters, the manufacturer receives a list of FabLabs from the partner matching module. He enters each of the FabLabs profiles, decides on the most suitable and makes a request for collaboration. The FabLab accepts and now the two partners sign a confidentiality agreement in order to safeguard the manufacturer's intellectual property and agree upon the terms of their collaboration (cost, time for prototype completion, quality and materials used). After the terms are agreed and all the legal documents exchanged, the manufacturer consider the FabLab to be a trusted

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member of the development process that can give recommendations on technical issues and related comments on the design. In other words, this is the point at which the manufacturer shares the whole design and toy idea.

When the technical characteristics of the design are finalised with the help of the FabLabs, the manufacturer contacts safety/environmental experts for another round of feedback. To contact safety/environmental experts, the manufacturer will once more use the Partner Matching module. He now feels confident to use the partner matching module himself instead of entering the Open Call section. Just like in the previous stage, he fills in the filters about the services he is looking for. He scrolls through the profiles of the Safety Experts that the partner matching module returned, and decides on the most suitable. If the Safety Expert accepts the request for collaboration, the two parties must sign a confidentiality agreement in this case as well before they can start sharing information.

At this point, the safety experts provide safety recommendations based on their experience and international standards so that the toy's (and packaging's) design can be considered safe for the age group that it is intended for. Moreover, environmental experts provide recommendations related to the toy's environmental implications that can affect, among others, the toy's material and the manufacturing process.

After the above stages are complete, the design is finalized and the manufacturer requests from FabLabs to proceed with prototyping based on the materials and processes that were agreed upon during the previous stages. The FabLabs create the prototypes, which they are enhanced with AR through ToyLabs Augmented Reality Engine. That means that after the prototype's construction, it can be possible for end-users (focus groups) to get a more realistic feeling of the product and provide additional feedback.

Next, the Safety Experts pre-certify the prototype or provide further recommendations for ensuring compliance with EU standards. Moreover, the environmental experts provide technical advice and manufacturer-specific recommendations regarding the reduction of the environmental impact of producing the toys. After some back and forth communication between the manufacturer and the experts the prototype is approved. At this point, the manufacturer (with the help of the platform) organizes some Focus groups so that end-users can interact with the toy prototype and give advice about improving it. Even though, the improvements will be minor and not radical, he feels that this is still a very important stage because it is the first contact that any end-user will have with the toy. Moreover, this stage is responsible for detecting the need for localized versions of the toy that will have greater potential in the local market. The manufacturer decides not to create any localized versions because this kind of toy is not suitable for such a purpose.

Then, the manufacturer uses the partner matching module once more to contact Childhood Experts that are members of the ToyLabs consortium for feedback. The

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partner matching module once more, allows the manufacturer to filter the results based on information such as qualification, expertise, skills and location. The last two phases of feedback (focus groups, Childhood experts) require the manufacturer to provide some incentives to those groups to ensure their participation. The manufacturer decides to offer free samples of the toy when it is finished to people that has an active role and provided useful recommendations about his product. Moreover, he decides to offer coupons for small discounts on his products just for participating in the focus groups. Finally, the platform includes a rating system that encourages experts and end-users to participate in the process and perform well. After describing his product one more and using the Partner Matching module he receives some responses. He rejects a few that have mediocre ratings and decides on those who can satisfy his needs the best.

At this point, the manufacturer has the final prototype and he is ready to proceed with the latter stages of product development (production, commercialization). Having the prototype, the manufacturer now proceeds to a sample production (pre-series production) of the final product that is made of the actual material that will be used later for mass-production. When the batch is ready, the manufacturer, collaborating with the FabLabs, organizes focus groups consisting of childhood experts for another round of feedback, concerning the operational assessment of the product. When this phase is complete, then another round of Safety/Environmental Assessment (on the final product and the localized versions, not the prototype) takes place. Finally, the manufacturer with the help of childhood experts organizes focus groups with end-users (i.e. children), who provide feedback that can be used later during the product's commercialization. What is noteworthy during the last phase of the product development process is that feedback is gathered (with the help of the ToyLabs platform) even after the product is ready for market. The manufacturer is very glad of this service because he feels that this feedback can lead to improvements on the product and the commercialization strategy. When the product is complete, the manufacturer can update its status to "Completed" and showcase it in the platform's static page for increased publicity.

3.4.2 FabLab's Perspective

A FabLab that is a member of the ToyLabs consortium wants to increase its potential business by helping toy manufacturers develop and prototype their products. The first thing it should do is log into the platform. After entering, he can see his ongoing projects at the starting dashboard as well as the stage of product development that each project is at. There is also an option that allows the FabLab to search for new work opportunities. This can happen in one of the following two ways. On the one hand, the FabLab receives a request (e.g. push notification, e-mail) from a Toy Manufacturer for the design of a new product. Such a request occurs, when the Toy Manufacturer used the Partner Matching module to search for potential partners and the FabLab's profile matched the services that the manufacturer requested. On the

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other hand, the FabLab may enter the Open Requests page of the platform and express its interest for a specific request the ToyLabs Partner Matching Component suggests.

When the FabLab, has picked a potential job, it sends the manufacturer a financial offer and waits for him to respond. If the response is positive, then the two parties must sign a confidentiality agreement so that the information exchanged between them is legally protected. After that, the manufacturer sends the FabLab the design of the product in 3D format using the AR component of the platform. As mentioned above, ToyLabs' AR component allows multiple designers to work on the same Virtual Environment which allows for seamless communication between the two parties. At this point, the FabLab, using its expertise will provide feedback on the parts of the design it disagrees with. After some back and forth communication between the manufacturer and the FabLab the design is finalized from a technical standpoint. That means that the two parties have agreed about the final version of the design as well as the materials and techniques used for the prototype.

Moreover, some FabLabs, having great experience in prototyping, already cooperate with Safety/Environmental experts. If that is the case, the FabLab can propose such potential collaborators that can give feedback to the manufacturer for the next stages of safety/environmental assessment. Of course, the manufacturer always retains the right to search for these services by using the Partner Matching module.

After the above stages are complete, the FabLab can proceed with the prototype of the requested design. Moreover, using Augmented Reality on top of the prototype, the FabLab can send a 3D representation of the prototype to the manufacturer and the two parties will exchange feedback once more until the prototype is finalized. Having the final prototype, the FabLab can now leverage its contacts to support feedback gathering from Security & Childhood experts in its region. Finally, after that feedback is collected, the need for localized versions of the toy will be assessed. If the manufacturer wants to proceed with the creation of localized versions of the toy, the FabLab is responsible for building the new prototypes and that concludes its role in the toy development process.

Nevertheless, that is not the only role of a FabLab in the platform. FabLabs can be product owners as well, meaning that a FabLab may design a new toy, prototype it and proceed by searching for a toy manufacturer that can mass produce this toy for the FabLab. In this case, the FabLab can make use of the Market Trends component to detect market trends and public opinions about its idea. Moreover, since the FabLab has the expertise to handle the design and prototype phases it will only use the partner matching module to locate Safety/environmental experts to give feedback for the prototype and a factory owner that can handle mass production. That means that in the ToyLabs platform, toy manufacturers can also act as providers of their factory's equipment for purposes of mass producing products that do not belong to the toy manufacturer. In that case, the FabLab can either make an open call describing the

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design and the services they require or use the partner matching module. In the latter case, the FabLab will be able to filter the results based on time for production, materials and equipment available and other characteristics of a toy manufacturer. The selected manufacturers will then have to provide financial offers and the one that will get the contract will have to sign a confidentiality agreement to protect the product's information. Finally, the FabLab and the manufacturer must agree on materials used, time for production and quality of the final product before the production can begin.

3.4.3 Safety Expert's Perspective

A safety expert (individual or organisation) wants to increase his potential business. He somehow (through the project's dissemination material) learns about the ToyLabs platform that requires the help of safety experts in the product development process. He decides to join the platform and see for himself if he can increase the amount of projects he works on through it. He visits the platform and signs up, filling in the information required (company name, role, certifications etc.) and soon enough he is a member of the ToyLabs platform. To find a potential collaboration opportunity, the safety expert visits the Open Call section of the Partner Matching module. He filters the results based on his profile and finds some projects that he can handle. He sends a message to the manufacturer declaring his interest in participating on the project. He attaches a financial offer and describes the services that he can offer to the manufacturer. Alternatively, the safety expert will receive a message from a manufacturer who used himself the partner matching module. That means that the manufacturer selected him from a handful of results. On either case, after some back and forth communication the manufacturer and the safety expert agree to collaborate. Thus, they sign a confidentiality agreement to legally protect the project's information.

The safety expert enters the process during the prototyping phase. He receives an enhanced AR model of the prototype from the FabLab that was already collaborating with the manufacturer. After studying the prototype, he offers advice and feedback concerning safety matters based on his experience and official EU safety standards. One of his advices is that the manufacturer should avoid having detachable small parts in the toy because the age group that the product is intended for is very young. He then sends his feedback to the manufacturer and the FabLab and agrees with them on a possible solution. The FabLab then creates another prototype and sends it back for more safety testing. When the prototype conforms to safety standards the role of the safety expert at this phase is complete. Nevertheless, he will remain in open communication with the rest of the stakeholders throughout the rest of the process.

As mentioned above, when the manufacturer has the final prototype he creates a sample production of the final product, which unlike the prototype is built using the actual material that was agreed for the product. At this point the safety expert is called again to provide feedback for the final product. If he finds a safety flaw in the final product, he sends his feedback to the manufacturer. In that case the process can go

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back to the prototyping or even the design phase. On the other hand, if the product has no safety issues but the safety expert still has some feedback for improving it, that feedback can be used in another development cycle that will have the purpose of creating an improved version of the current toy.

3.5 GENERALISED REQUIREMENTS IDENTIFICATION

This chapter aims at generating the high-level user requirements that will be used for the definition of the methodology and the design of the platform's features. To generate the requirements, input from D1.1: Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains and ToyLabs Concept Definition is used, and the pilots' and the interviews/questionnaires from the platform's stakeholders. The structure of this chapter is as follows:

First, the three basic modules of the platform (Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component, Partner Matching Module and Augmented Reality Module) are described, as well as their necessary key features, and the general functionalities of the ToyLabs' platform.

Following the above, the requirements and key features that the system must have during a new product development process are presented. The procedure will follow the same steps as the stages of product development (Immersion & Concept Definition, Design, Prototype, Sample Production and Commercialisation) and each step will have different functionalities and include a specific number of the platform's basic modules. However, although it might seem like the modules can be used only in the specific phases that they are assigned to, they can also be used as standalone tools within the platform by registered users at their convenience.

3.5.1 Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component

3.5.1.1 General Description

The Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component is one of the three key modules of the ToyLabs platform. It performs sentiment analysis and concept extraction on social media (Facebook, twitter) and other online channels (blogs, forums etc.) that are related to the toy industry. "*Sentiment analysis is the process of computationally identifying and categorizing opinions expressed in a piece of text, especially in order to determine whether the writer's attitude towards a particular topic, product, etc. is positive, negative or neutral*"³. In the scope of the ToyLabs platform, this module is used mainly in the stage of Immersion & Concept Definition to help uncover the public opinion about a product/idea. The platform's user, during this stage, trying to validate the potential of an idea/concept he has, will initialise the module, and

³ https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/sentiment_analysis

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after selecting the online channels and terms that he wants to search for, will receive useful analytics that will help him realise the public opinion about those terms.

3.5.1.2 Main Features

In this sub-chapter, the main features of the Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component Engine will be mentioned. Most of the following features are essential for making this module functional:

- A. Selection between trend detection (identification of trends around the concept) and social feedback analysis (identification of feedback around a company/product)
- B. Ability to initiate a comparative trends analysis in which the manufacturer will be able to view a comparison of the results between two different concepts
- C. Selection of social media channels (Facebook, twitter)
- D. Selection of other web sources (blogs, forums)
- E. Selection of concepts and topics for search
- F. Decision on the language of interest
- G. Enable/disable influencer mode
- H. Initialise module
- I. See visualised analytics

3.5.1.3 Stakeholders

The Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component will be mainly used during the stage of Immersion & Concept Definition by the person/organisation (that will usually be a manufacturer) that has a new concept for a toy in order to uncover the public opinion behind this idea. However, any user of the platform may have access to the full functionality of the module if they are certified by the platform. The rest of the users who are not certified by the platform as stakeholders of the product development process will also be able to access the module's more basic functionalities.

3.5.2 Partner Matching Module

3.5.2.1 General Description

One of the key issues that were detected during the interview/questionnaire phase, as well as the Pilots' Requirements Identification phase is the difficulty that toy manufacturers have in finding reliable collaborators that can help them during the product development process. For that reason, a Partner matching module will be implemented in the platform to enable ToyLabs' users to search for potential collaborators. The module will work by applying sophisticated criteria, and to propose the right stakeholders for the specific strategic needs of the user in question. The partner matching process, much like the trends analysis process may be repeated as

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many times as necessary, thus helping the user in finding the right partners in a timely and cost-effective manner.

3.5.2.2 Main Features

The main functions that need to be included in the Partner Matching Module are the following:

- A. Initialise module and search for partners
- B. See a list of collaborators suggested by partners he already works with
- C. Invite a partner to a step of the process
- D. See all partners that have signed an NDA to a product
- E. Make an Open Request
- F. Attach NDA to open request
- G. View responses from open request
- H. Select suitable partners
- I. Decline responses from open requests
- J. Accept a signed contract from a collaborator
- K. See all partners that have signed a collaboration contract for a product

3.5.2.3 Stakeholders

The following table lists all the stakeholders that will use the Partner Matching Module as well as the specific features intended for each of them:

Stakeholder	Features / Stakeholder
Manufacturer	A-K
FabLabs	G- J
Safety/Environmental Experts	G- J

3.5.3 Augmented Reality Module

3.5.3.1 General Description

The Augmented Reality Module will be mainly used during prototyping. Given that the FabLab building the prototype will not always be geographically close to the manufacturer's organisation and that the prototype may have many iterations, this module will be used to project digital information on an image of the prototype to receive feedback by the manufacturer and the other stakeholders. This tool is integral

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to the value proposition of the platform as it helps ensure continuous communication and feedback gathering between the collaborating parties during a new product development process. The main features of the module as well as the platform's stakeholders that will use it are presented in the next sub-chapters.

3.5.3.2 Main Features

- A. Attach an AR model to a prototype
- B. Accompany the AR model with a simple questionnaire for AR user
- C. Upload a screenshot of AR model
- D. Comment on an AR model
- E. Vote for specific features on an AR model on mobile devices (FabLab, experts)
- F. Manipulate controls of the AR model

3.5.3.3 Stakeholders

The following table lists the different stakeholder teams that will use the Augmented Reality Module as well as the specific functionalities intended for each team:

Stakeholder	Features
Manufacturer	A, B, C
FabLabs	C, D, E, F
Safety/Environmental Experts	C, D, E, F
Childhood Experts/End-Users	C, D, E, F

3.5.4 ToyLabs Platform

The ToyLabs platform, apart from the features that deal with the new product development process, also includes several core functions that will be explained in the sub-chapters below.

3.5.4.1 Sign Up

A user of the platform (manufacturer, FabLab, expert etc.) must be able to sign up to the platform. He can only register himself, or himself and the organisation he works for/owns, in case his organisation is not registered. If it is, then he should be able to join the organisation in the platform after getting the approval of its officer. If he

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is not a member of such an organisation, the user can ask for validation from the platform if he feels like he has something to offer to a product development process (i.e. if he is a freelancing safety expert).

3.5.4.2 Log In/Log Out/Profile Settings

After signing up, the user should be able to sign in and out of the platform at will, without a problem. Furthermore, he must be able to edit his personal profile information as well as to specify some basic, optional personal profile information, such as his role in the platform (Expert, Certified User, Manufacturer etc.), so that he can enjoy the services offered to the role that he belongs to. Finally, he should be able to permanently remove his account from the system so that he can no longer be contacted by users of the platform if he so desires.

3.5.4.3 Dashboard

When logging in to the platform, a certified user will be able to see the home dashboard, from where he can view information about himself and the projects that he is working on, as well as being able to access the platform's functionalities relevant to his role. The different functions of the ToyLabs platform dashboard will be explained with greater detail in the following sub-chapters. Moreover, there will be a separate sub-chapter that will describe the different features that a visitor of the platform (not a certified user) will be able to access.

3.5.4.4 Active/Ongoing/Following Projects

The first thing that a certified user (manufacturer, FabLab, expert) of the platform will be able to see at the home dashboard are the active and ongoing projects that he has initiated or participates in, as well as the stage of product development that they are currently in. By selecting them, the system will direct him to the current phase of the project and provide additional information depending on his access level and role. Furthermore, he will be able to follow a product that he is interested in by hitting the "like" button and view the products that he follows in a separate screen. The details that will be available for products that are not assigned to him will be limited by the owner of the product and the platform itself. Finally, he will get notified when a product makes an announcement to its followers allowing him to get instant news about it.

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3.5.4.4.1 Rating System

The platform will include a rating system that users can use to rate their partners based on how satisfied they were with their cooperation and the end results. The rating system will be explained below:

- 1) ToyLabs rating experience
 - a. The manufacturer will be able to rate his stakeholders so that later, they get points based on feedback.
 - b. The manufacturer/FabLab/toy safety expert/end user will be able to rate his overall platform experience
- 2) Unsatisfied user: If a manufacturer is unsatisfied with the stakeholder that he chooses to cooperate with, he can decide to continue the process with a different stakeholder and to receive a standard discount from the platform.
- 3) Satisfied user: If the manufacturer is satisfied with the result he should be able to get a discount for his next project if he advertises ToyLabs through social media or press releases.

3.5.4.4.2 Toy Industry Reports & Data Repository

The platform will include an open library where certified users may upload files relevant to toy development which will be organised and available to all other certified users. These files can include safety standards, price lists, brand names etc.

3.5.4.4.3 New Project Option

By clicking on the “Create New Project” button, a registered user can become a product owner and initiate a product creation phase.

3.5.4.5 UI for Visitors

A visitor must be able to find out more about the ToyLabs project from the main platform and go through a short tutorial/help page on how the ToyLabs platform operates. Moreover he must be able to sign up to the platform by offering minimal details (name, username, e-mail, and password) or sign up using his social media (Facebook, twitter) credentials. After signing up he should be able to see the Terms of Use of the platform and the NDA (Non-Disclosure Agreement). If he accepts those terms then he should be accepted to the platform. If he has an issue about the terms and NDA he must be able to contact the platform’s operators through a form. Moreover, he will be able to see all public designs and prototypes of ToyLabs in the main platform and sort them based on the date of their creation and their popularity. Furthermore, he will be able to visit the static page in which finished products are being showcased and links to the manufacturer’s website are provided. Finally, there will be options to change the accessibility options on the website’s content.

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3.5.5 Immersion & Concept Definition

This chapter describes the first stage of ToyLabs' new product development process, which is the stage of Immersion & Concept Definition as well as the basic features that must be included in it. This phase includes the brainstorming that is necessary to come up with a novel idea for a new product and is traditionally performed without using external tools. In the ToyLabs platform it is recognized that the basic idea for a new toy belongs to the manufacturer most of the times. However, a Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component, which will be based on concept extraction and sentiment analysis, will be included, thus helping him realise the potential success of his idea by getting feedback from online sources. In other words, when starting a new project, the manufacturer will be directed to the Immersion & Concept Definition Stage in which he will be able to select the "Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component" to collect feedback. Apart from that, this module will also be able to help a manufacturer, who wishes to develop a new idea, but is not yet clear on the specific product that he wants to develop. In that case, he will be able, with the module's help, to detect upcoming trends that are worth investing, or even products and ideas that do not perform well at that time, thus discouraging him from pursuing them. The basic requirements of the Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component will be described in the next sub-chapters.

3.5.5.1 Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component

ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component is one of the main tools of the platform. It helps the manufacturer collect feedback from online sources about an idea and its usefulness can be seen by the following three scenarios:

1. The manufacturer has a very specific idea which means that he knows what he wants to develop. As a result, he wishes to learn if the public has a positive/negative opinion about this specific idea.
2. The manufacturer has little idea about what he wants to develop. However, he knows the domain/type of toy that he wants to produce. As a result, his search will be more general and the module will return products/ideas in this domain/type of toy that are performing well/bad.
3. The manufacturer wants to redevelop an existing toy in his inventory hoping to improve it. In this case, he will be able to search using specific filters about his existing toy (his company name, toy name etc.) to collect feedback about the public opinion concerning that toy and recommendations/trends that could be incorporated in his new design.

There are four basic features that the ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component should include that will be described in the next sub-chapters:

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1. Ability to select between trend detection (identification of trends around the concept) and social feedback analysis (identification of feedback around a company/product),
2. Ability to initiate a comparative trends analysis in which the manufacturer will be able to view a comparison of the results between two different concepts,
3. Ability to select the social media sources that will be searched,
4. Ability to select via filters the terms/phrases that should be searched,
5. Ability to enable/disable “influencer mode”,
6. A dashboard to visualise the results.

The user will have to make selections in the first five features before he can initialise the module. The results will be shown in the dashboard after the analysis is complete.

3.5.5.1.1 Trend Detection & Social Feedback Analysis

The Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component will give the manufacturer the ability to choose between two different modes of analysis. On the one hand, he will be able to perform trend detection which is the identification of trends around a concept/idea (which by default is more abstract). On the other hand, the system allows social feedback analysis which is the identification of feedback/opinions around a more specific product or even the company itself.

3.5.5.1.2 Comparative Trends Analysis

In the case that the manufacturer chooses to perform trend detection, he will have the choice to perform comparative trend detection. Specifically, he will be able to insert two different concepts and see comparative visualised analytics (i.e. graphs) which will help him realise the potential of each one.

3.5.5.1.3 Social Media Sources

One of the things that the manufacturer should set when working with the Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component is to select the social media/web sources that he is interested in searching in. As a result, the module must include online places where opinions and information about specific products and the toy industry in general are exchanged. The manufacturer will have the capability to search in all the included sources but usually he will be interested in specific information. Consequently, we will list below the online sources that will be included for search in the module:

1. Social Media (Facebook, Twitter etc.)
2. Other web sources (Blogs, Forums, Pages etc.)

3.5.5.1.4 Search Capabilities

The main functionality of ToyLabs’ Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component is allowing the manufacturer to search in online sources based on filters

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and terms/concepts that he chooses. After selecting the sources that he wants to search from, he will have to fill in the specific words related to the idea/product that he wants to develop.

3.5.5.1.5 Influencer Mode

During the trend analysis, the manufacturer must be able to enable/disable influencer mode. On social media, influencers are people with a bigger than usual fan base, whose opinions can also influence the opinion of their followers and fans. As a result, the module's user at this point will be encouraged to disable "influencer mode" when he is searching for feedback about a specific product/idea because he will be more interested in the customers' opinions. On the other hand, in more general searches (when he does not know exactly what he wants to develop), he will be encouraged to enable influencer mode.

3.5.5.1.6 Visual Dashboard

After the analysis is complete, ToyLabs' Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component will include a dashboard where the results can be seen and visualised. Moreover, this feature will include an option that allows the manufacturer to reinitialise his search, if he is not satisfied with the results, by modifying one or more of his previous choices without having to begin the procedure from scratch. Finally, when he is happy with the feedback collected/trends identified, he can save the results and move on to the next phase or save the results and perform more analyses with different search criteria.

3.5.6 Design

Following Immersion & Concept Definition, the design of a new product is probably the most crucial phase of toys development. Instead of considering design as an internal operation of the toy manufacturer, ToyLabs proposes an enhanced iterative design process based on collaboration with external parties who belong in the ToyLabs network. This phase will be responsible for the design of both the product and its packaging, and by the end of it, the most important issues concerning the design will have to be addressed. To achieve that, the manufacturer will use the Partner Matching module that will allow him to locate collaborating parties that can help him achieve this task by offering feedback and addressing issues of the design. This process can be repeated as many times as needed to make sure, at this early stage, that the design has absolutely no issues regarding its required manufacturing process, since usually such issues are being discovered at a later stage costing to the SMEs both money and valuable time.

When entering the design phase, the manufacturer will be able to see the following functions:

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1. A place in which the manufacturer can upload his product design in some form of 3D representation
2. A place in which the manufacturer can upload his packaging design in some form of 3D representation.
3. A button that allows him to initialise the partner matching module in order to search for possible collaborators that can help him in the design phase. The partner matching module will help the him locate the following groups of experts:
 - a. FabLabs that will help co-design the product and manufacture the prototype
 - b. Safety Experts that make sure the product design is up to toy safety standards
 - c. Environmental Experts that give recommendations concerning the materials used and the procedures followed to decrease the procedure's environmental footprint.

The specific functionalities that this module will include will be described in the next sub-chapters.

4. A place in which the manufacturer can upload the design of the prototype that the FabLab will manufacture.

When in the design phase, on the one hand, the manufacturer has the choice to upload his designs for the product and the packaging before searching for possible collaborators that can provide feedback and recommendations. Alternatively, he can first find the experts he needs, explain to them his idea and cooperatively design the product and the packaging with their help. In other words, the procedure will be fully flexible depending on his needs and preferences. It must be mentioned that the whole procedure will be closed and not visible to members of the platform that the manufacturer does not cooperate with at that time. However, he will be able to turn the visibility of a "Design" version to the public (if he is interested in early feedback from the public), that will showcase only basic design information.

3.5.6.1 Initial Product Design

When in the design phase's dashboard, the first thing that the manufacturer is encouraged to do is upload his design for the product that he wants to develop. The way it works, is that he will be able to create a "Master" design which he can then populate with multiple different versions of the design. By pressing the "add design" button, he will then have to choose between local file upload and online source file. Moreover, there will be a message informing him about the acceptable formats that he can upload as well as the maximum file size. As already mentioned, the manufacturer will not be limited to one file upload but can upload different iterations of his design so that he can go back to a previous one if he wishes to. Furthermore, he will have the ability to delete previous iterations of his design that he does not use anymore, by

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pressing a “remove” button next to the design file. Finally, he will be able to populate a “Design” version with material relevant to this phase and version (files, specifications, cost, analyses etc.).

3.5.6.2 Initial Package Design

Much like with the initial product design, the manufacturer will be prompted to upload his design for the packaging as early as possible because it is also crucial for cost and safety issues. The procedure remains the same as above, as far as the uploading is concerned. However, the packaging will be paired with a product design, meaning that the manufacturer will have the ability to pair multiple packaging designs with a single product design, have multiple product designs paired with the same packaging, or use a combination of those techniques. Finally, he will be able to delete packaging designs by pressing a “remove” button next to the design. This button will only delete the packaging design, whereas the same button in the product design will not only delete the design of the product but also of the corresponding packages that were paired with it. For that reason, before deleting anything, the system will warn the user with a message about the files that he is about to delete to avoid mistakes.

3.5.6.3 Partner Matching Module

The partner matching module is responsible for creating collaboration relationships between the platform’s stakeholders. It works by applying sophisticated criteria, to propose the right stakeholders for the specific strategic needs of the SME in question. The partner matching module can be used in one of the following ways:

1. Searching mode, which allows a user to search for the right stakeholders on his own by using specific filters that are relevant to the services that he needs from a potential partner.
2. Open Request which allows the user to describe his problem/needs along with the specific partners he is looking for. Once complete, his request will be moved to the Open Request page which will be accessible by the FabLabs and the other experts looking for potential collaboration opportunities.

The specific features of the module in the design phase will be explained with greater detail in the following sub-chapters.

Finally, it must be mentioned that the partner selection process can be repeated as many times as needed to come up with such partner selection that may lead to the desired network objectives in a timely and cost-efficient manner.

3.5.6.3.1 Initialize Partner Matching Module

When the manufacturer is in the design phase’s dashboard, he has the choice to initialise the Partner Matching module by pressing a button. The platform will then redirect him in the next screen where he will be presented with the following options:

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1. In case he is already collaborating with experts that use the platform he will be able to see a list of possible collaborators suggested by the partners he already works with. In that case, he can view the profiles of the suggested partners and decide whether he wants to collaborate with them or not.
2. Create an Open Request call for collaborators, in which he describes what he needs and what he is looking for and waits for replies.
3. Search for partners himself by selecting what kind of expert he wants to find and then filling up the rest of the information that he will be prompted by the system.

Depending on the choice he makes, the manufacturer will then be redirected to another page that will be described later.

3.5.6.3.2 Searching Mode

The Partner Matching module's searching mode allows the user to search for a list of potential partners by specifying his exact needs and filling up the module's filters accordingly. Depending on the partner that he is searching for, the filters that he will have to fill in will be different. First he will have to decide what kind of partner he is looking for:

- 1) Manufacturer (in case he is a manufacturer himself and is searching for a provider of mass manufacturing capabilities)
- 2) FabLabs
- 3) Safety/Environmental Experts
- 4) Childhood Experts

Following that he will be able to fill in additional filters concerning required services, toy category, technical competencies, locations/facilities, certifications/qualifications, economic criteria etc.

When the user is done filling in the filters he can press the submit button that will redirect him to the result page which will be described with greater detail later.

3.5.6.3.3 Open Request Page

If the user chooses to launch an "Open Request" call for collaborators then he will be redirected to the Open Request page. Given that the product owner is not always a manufacturer (in fact it can be a designer/user/FabLab searching for a manufacturer), this page is different for the user making the call and the rest of the stakeholders (manufacturers, FabLabs, experts) that are searching for collaboration opportunities.

- **Manufacturer Perspective** (in case he is the product owner): For the manufacturer, the Open request page will resemble the searching mode, meaning that he will have to fill in information about his design and the collaborator that he is searching for. More specifically, he will have to initially

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select the type of partner that he wants to find and the capabilities of this partner. Moreover, he can include the design of his product, since the platform includes a mechanism capable of protecting his intellectual property. Specifically, the platform allows him to attach an NDA (non-Disclosure Agreement) to the Open Request. Once the request is complete, then any stakeholder that wishes to see the request (and its relevant information) will have to first agree to the NDA, thus safeguarding the manufacturer's design from leaking outside of the agreed upon partners. By pressing the submit button, the Partner matching module is initialised and the user is redirected to the results page where he can see all the possible partners that meet his standards.

- **Manufacturer Perspective (in case he is not the product owner):** When the manufacturer is not the main product owner, which means that he is acting as a potential partner who can have a consulting role during the process as well as handle the mass manufacturing of the product in the cases that the product owner's organisation does not possess mass manufacturing capabilities. In that case, the manufacturer can browse through the Open Request call and given that his profile states that he is a manufacturer, the results will be already filtered. As a consequence, he will only see requests that are related to consulting services and mass manufacturing. Moreover, there will be filters that allow him to sort the results by date added, development stage etc. When clicking on a potential request, the manufacturer will sometimes have to sign an NDA (when the product owner has specified so) and if he thinks that he can handle the requested services he can press a relevant button in order to make a request for collaboration. All of the manufacturer's requests will be visible on his starting dashboard.
- **FabLab Perspective:** When a FabLab enters the Open Request section, he will be able to see requests related to prototype manufacturing, co-design and consultancy services. He can filter the results based on date added, manufacturing process and material etc. All of the FabLab's requests are visible on his starting dashboard.
- **Safety/Environmental Expert:** Much like in the previous cases, a Safety/Environmental Expert must be able to browse through the Open Request section where he will be able to see requests asking for consulting services relevant to safety/environmental issues. All of the expert's requests are visible on his starting dashboard.

3.5.6.3.4 Visual Dashboard

1. **Searching Mode:** When the user, has submitted a partner matching search he will be redirected to a visual dashboard where he can see all the eligible results. He can enter and view the results' profiles, reject the ones that he does not find suitable and place others in higher priority for better organisation purposes. He

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will be able to invite a partner to a step of the toy creation process and see all his requests on his dashboard.

2. **Open Request:** When a user makes an Open Request instead, then his dashboard will show the responses from potential partners. He can filter them by type (manufacturer, FabLab, experts) and select which partners to invite to the toy creation process. Moreover, in case he has attached an NDA to the request, he can choose to view responses only from those partners who signed the NDA contract. When he has started signing collaboration contracts, he will be able to see all partners that have signed a contract to the product.

3.5.6.3.5 Agreement Phase

When the user has located suitable collaborators, he can start exchanging the necessary documents in order to start collaborating with the partner. If he has not attached an NDA to the Open Request, he has the option to do so when he sends the contract to the partner. Moreover, if the partner sends him a signed contract first, he should be able to accept (double sign) it. Finally, when a collaboration contract has been signed, the partner should be able to download all material in a “Design” version that he has been invited to.

3.5.6.3.6 Incentives for Continuous Collaboration

When the user has had a successful collaboration with a partner, the platform faces the danger that the two partners will continue collaborating outside of the platform. To safeguard the platform against such phenomena, the stakeholders (mainly FabLabs and safety/environmental experts) will be urged to offer discounts and benefits to returning customers in order to keep their business. Moreover, the platform will advertise returning inventor’s/manufacturer’s work (if he is willing) to social media, toy fairs and the press.

3.5.6.4 *Prototype Design*

The prototype design is a different phase from the product’s design, because usually the prototype is constructed using different techniques and materials compared to the original product. For that reason, the collaborating partners (FabLabs, experts), after downloading the required material will be able to provide feedback by directly and privately contacting the manufacturer. The same procedure is followed for the design of the final product as well, at least at this stage of the process. The platform will offer private back and forth communication between two partners and after all the feedback has been received and implemented by the manufacturer the product is ready for the prototype phase.

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3.5.7 Feasibility Study & IPR Check

This is an intermediary phase that can take place before or at the same time as the design phase. It includes a feasibility study in which the manufacturer evaluates the economic feasibility of his design while also checking if it violates any IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) of other products.

3.5.7.1 Feasibility Study

The feasibility study aims at helping the manufacturer realize the ballpark cost of his product development process. For that reason, as soon as the right collaborators for his process are found, he has the right to ask them for the prices they normally offer for the services that he has requested. The feasibility study will include costs related to: FabLab's consulting services, Safety/Environmental experts' consulting services, cost for organising focus groups, prototype cost, possible localization cost, prototype transfer cost (in case the FabLab is located in another country) and cost for mass manufacturing of the product and the packaging (which can be given by the manufacturing partner in case the user does not have manufacturing capabilities).

3.5.7.2 IPR Check

The IPR check is included for procedures like the TRADE name selection procedure so that the manufacturer can be sure that the name of his product does not violate any intellectual property rights of other products. For that reason, the platform will provide the capability to check the European Union's toy databases and search if a given name already exists, thus saving the manufacturer from a lot of trouble down the road.

3.5.8 Prototype

After addressing all design issues, the process goes on with the development of the product's prototype by one or more FabLabs that participate in the project. Traditionally, the prototype is created in the production facilities of the SME manufacturer, which however is a process taking much time and effort since such facilities are ideal for mass production but not for rapid prototyping both in terms of time and cost. By using one or more FabLabs to perform the same procedure, the prototype is developed in facilities capable of producing single complicated items at minimum time and limited cost. Moreover, the prototypes themselves can be validated be representative samples of local users and the option for localized versions of the toy can be examined as well. This phase is reliant on two parameters: use of the Augmented Reality module for sending realistic 3D designs of the prototype to the manufacturer and the experts and use of the Partner Matching module to locate childhood experts that can organize focus groups to validate the prototype. More details on the specific features included in this phase will be given in the next sub-

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chapters. Apart from those two modules, there are some general functions that will be visible when the manufacturer and the other stakeholders enter this phase after the design phase. For the manufacturer:

- The manufacturer will be able to transfer the design versions that he wishes from the design phase to the prototype phase. Next to each of the design version will appear a button that lets him create a new prototype based on that specific version of the design.
- He will be able to turn the visibility of a prototype version to public (if he wants early feedback from end-users) that will showcase only basic design information.
- He will be able to populate the prototype version with information and material relevant to it (files, specifications, cost, analyses etc.).

For the FabLabs and safety/environmental experts:

- They must be able to download all available material of a prototype that they have been invited to by pressing a button next to it
- They must be able to directly and privately contact the manufacturer about a prototype using the platform's communication tools.

3.5.8.1 Augmented Reality

Augmented Reality is an enhanced version of reality created by the use of technology to overlay digital information on an image of something being viewed through a device (such as a smartphone camera).⁴ Under the scope of the ToyLabs platform the Augmented Reality module that will be implemented will be used to receive valuable feedback on the prototypes and 3D designs. The specific features that are relevant to the AR module for the different stakeholder groups are listed below:

- 1) The manufacturer must be able to:
 - a. Attach an Augmented Reality model to a prototype
 - b. Accompany the Augmented Reality model with a simple questionnaire for the AR user in order to help him organize his feedback
 - c. View the feedback sent by the collaborators on the prototype
- 2) The FabLabs and the Safety/Environmental experts must be able to:
 - a. Comment on the AR model in the ToyLabs platform. The comments can be seen by the manufacturer and depending on his privacy settings by the other collaborating parties as well
 - b. Vote specific features on an AR model on their mobile devices for instant feedback
 - c. Upload screenshots of the AR model in order to show the product owner their display of the model

⁴ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/augmented%20reality>

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- 3) Only the FabLabs will be able to play with controls embedded in the AR model to enhance their experience with the conceptual model which can lead to more solid feedback.
- 4) Finally the Safety/Environmental experts will be able at this stage to pre-certify the product based on the AR model or provide further recommendations for ensuring compliance with safety and environmental standards.

3.5.8.2 Partner Matching

The manufacturer, at this stage will be able to use the partner matching module once more in search of childhood experts that will perform another round of feedback. The process will be the same (with slight changes on the filters used) as in the previous cases of partner matching. When he finds the right experts and they accept the request for collaboration, they will have to sign an NDA contract and the collaboration contract as well. At that point they can download all the information needed so they can better understand the product, in order to provide their feedback. Additional functionalities at this phase include:

- **Focus Groups:** The childhood experts, apart from giving their own feedback can also organize focus groups with potential end-users of the toy. This can be done by using their own circle of stakeholders (schools, parents unions etc.) or with the help of the platform. In the latter case, the childhood expert, with the manufacturer's permission, can make an Open Request, calling upon the platform's users to participate to an online round of feedback that will be done with the help of the Augmented Reality module. The users, if they accept, must sign an NDA contract as well, to safeguard the product owner's IPRs.

Focus groups can also be organized by the FabLabs, without the help of the childhood experts. Specifically, after the prototype is manufactured, the FabLabs can present it to their local TSIG in order to get useful recommendations about possible design modifications, while also exploring the need for localized versions. The feedback is collected by the FabLabs and sent to the product owner who decides about the next steps of the process.

- **Incentives:** These rounds of feedback (Childhood experts, focus groups) require the manufacturer to offer some incentives in order to ensure their participation. The platform offers such functionality allowing him to attach files that specify prizes depending on the level of participation of the user (free samples for recommendations that will be implemented, discount coupons for participation etc.). Moreover, the platform includes a rating system that extends to Childhood experts and end-users as well, thus incentivising them to respect the process.
- **Localized Versions:** The aforementioned focus groups, especially when performed in more than one country, are an excellent opportunity to examine the need for localized versions of the toy. If there is such a recommendation

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and the manufacturer accepts it, then he can add one or multiple localized versions to the current prototype version by pressing a specific button. The localized version can be manufactured immediately by the FabLabs or it can go through all the previous stages of design and safety/environmental assessment as well (although this process is completely optional).

3.5.9 Sample Production

After finalizing all the details about the prototype and the localized versions the manufacturer will be able to proceed to a sample production (pre-series production) of the final product and initialize another round of feedback, this time on the final product (since all previous feedback was performed on the prototype). This feedback includes another round of focus groups and safety/environmental checks. When these processes are done the final product will be ready for mass production and commercialisation.

The **safety/environmental assessment** of the final product will be conducted by the same experts that were identified with the help of the Partner Matching module during the previous phases. The experts will be able to enter the Sample Production page, click on the final product and evaluate it with the help of the information attached to it. For a more hands on assessment, the experts will have to contact the manufacturer via the platform's communication system and ask for a product sample to be shipped to them.

The focus groups, as was mentioned in the previous chapter can be conducted by the FabLabs, Childhood experts or the manufacturer himself with the help of the platform. The participants of those focus groups will ideally be end-users of the targeted age demographic and they will give the manufacturer a clear idea of how people will react to his product.

3.5.10 Market

When the product is ready for market, the manufacturer can mark it as released and update its description. Moreover, the platform will include an online space where products constructed with the help of the ToyLabs platform can be showcased to end-consumers. The manufacturer will be able to advertise his product via the platform and provide a link for his website. The static page will provide the capability to filter the products shown by toy category, popularity, date added, price etc.

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4 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

Part A of the present deliverable was responsible for defining a novel framework for requirement elicitation as well as presenting the high-level user requirements for the ToyLabs platform.

For the first part, after the identification of the platform's stakeholders (drawing from the toy industry stakeholders identified during the first deliverable), a novel methodology for requirement identification was presented. This methodology was based on existing tried methodologies, mainly waterfall and agile as well as techniques and methods identified during online research (questionnaires, interviews, use cases). It was important at that stage, to take into consideration the small duration of the ToyLabs project and its need to be open to modification and changes as far as requirements are concerned. That is the reason why a combination of waterfall and agile techniques was used. As a result, it can be concluded that the defined methodology adequately serves the needs of the project.

Following that, the pilots of the project were presented in order to understand their processes, their current challenges and ToyLabs proposition in dealing with those challenges. Moreover, drawing from the pilots, a number of high-level use case scenarios were developed that describe how each team of stakeholders (manufacturers, FabLabs, experts) will use the platform, in which stages of product development as well as the services that the platform will offer them.

The last part of the present deliverable had to do with the definition of the high-level user requirements. For this procedure, input was taken by the work and techniques used in the earlier parts of the deliverable as well as discussions with the project's partners. The requirements were analysed at first, under the scope of the main project modules (Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component, Partner Matching Module, Augmented Reality module) and then under the scope of the platform itself and the phases of new product development. It must be mentioned at this point, that while the general requirements defined in this deliverable (that are key in the project's value proposition) will not change, and their specific features are open to modifications and additions in the present deliverable's second iteration.

Finally, in latter deliverables, the high-level requirements identified in the present deliverable, will be analysed further and turned into more specific technical and business requirements which in turn will become the features of the platform during the development phases.

PART B: VALIDATION FRAMEWORK DETERMINATION

5 INTRODUCTION

This part of the deliverable is responsible for the analysis of validation methodologies as well as the definition of the ToyLabs validation framework and the criteria and performance indicators that will be used to measure the impact of the project in solving the problems identified in EU's toy manufacturing sector. Drawing from the extensive experience acquired from related projects, it was managed to define a suitable validation methodology that acted as the guide for completing the different steps needed to define the objectives of the different platform stakeholders and the performance indicators that will measure and the criteria that will validate them.

5.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

Part B of D1.1 is structured in 4 chapters that provide the main information concerning the Validation Framework Determination such as the general methodology used and the specific criteria that will be used to measure the project's impact.

Chapter 5 is just the introduction to the document. It starts by mentioning the goals of T1.4. Moreover, it includes the structure of this document and the points of interaction between this deliverable and other Work Packages and tasks.

Chapter 6 is initially focused on identifying and classifying the most current Business Performance Indicator Methods (BPIM). Additionally, it will categorise them into four different categories. Finally, special mention will be given to the ECOGRAI method on which the project's validation methodology will be based.

Chapter 7 will work on the definition of the ECOGRAI simplified method which will be used for the project's validation. Additionally, it will describe, following this method, all the necessary information for business validation such as objectives and key performance indicators.

Chapter 8 collects the conclusions of the document while chapter 9 contains the detailed bibliography.

5.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The structure of the deliverable is grouped into 2 major blocks; according to the objectives described in section 5.1 (see **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia..1**):

Figure 5-1 - Structure of the Deliverable

Block A has the function to introduce the ToyLabs Validation process approach and integrate the topic into the project context.

Block B contains the entirety of the Validation Framework Determination. Specifically, this is the part of the document where the Validation Framework will be defined as well as the criteria that will be used in order to calculate the project's impact and added value to each stakeholder.

Block C includes the conclusions of Part B where the results are summarized and guidelines for the next steps are provided.

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5.3 RELATION TO OTHER TOYLABS WPS AND TASKS

During experimentation in WP5 the criteria and performance indicators described in this deliverable are collected and in T5.4 are interpreted to assess the research success and the innovation impact of the project.

6 DETERMINATION OF BUSINESS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS METHODS FOR TOYLABS

This paragraph is divided in two parts. The first part categorizes and classifies the most current Business Performance Indicator Methods (BPIM). In the second part, a description of ECOGRAI will be given. ECOGRAI is the method on which ToyLabs Validation framework will be based on. As a result, this method will be described in this chapter and emphasis will be given on its strengths and the phases comprising it.

6.1 BUSINESS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS METHODS

There are numerous methods nowadays that are proposed by researchers and practitioners in the literature devoted to the performance area. Most of these methods were developed in the past (before the year 2000) but there are more developed every year by researchers who take into account the new developments both in ICT and in Validation methodologies. In this chapter, a few current performance measurement methods, some more well-known and used than others will be presented and categorized.

The methods will be categorized in four (not exclusive) categories based on their most dominant design characteristics. The term “not exclusive” is used because some methods can fall into two or more of these categories.

A) Methods with a basic architecture of performance measurements (A)

These methods present a structure comprising of internal and external dimensions of predetermined performance indicators and they help managers and employees focus on these essential independent performance factors. Generally the approaches are balanced. Ex: BSC (Balanced Score Card) (Kaplan and Norton 2005);PPMMatrix (Keegan et al. 1989);SMART Pyramid (Lynch and Cross 1991) etc.

B) Methods with a methodology for Performance Indicators System design and implementation (B)

The second category of methods provides well-structured methodologies with explicit guide lines and step by step procedure comprised processes for choosing

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the indicators and the PIs implementation. Ex: ECOGRAI (Bitton and Doumeingts 1990), GIMSI (Fernandez 2003), IPMF (Medori and Steeple 2000); etc.

C) Methods with diagnosis for improvement (C).

These methods use audits in order to find the domains of performance which require improvements. They help decision makers determine the functions and elements that require improvements and the criteria on which the company must concentrate its improvement efforts on, in order to maintain its success. Ex: PMQ (Dixon et al. 1990); TOPP (MOSENG and BREDRUP 1993); IDPMS (Ghalayini et al. 1997); etc.

D) Methods based on organisation models to support the selection of performance dimensions (D)

The last category of methods helps in the choosing of PIs according to the structures of the company/ organization as well as the domains of performance on which the indicators must be assigned. Ex: ENAPS (Bradley and Jordan 1996); EFQM (EFQM 1998); SCOR (Stewart 1997); etc.

Classification of BPIs methods according to the type of framework

This part of the document contains a brief SOTA analysis of Validation Frameworks. As a result, a framework will be built that will include many “recommendations” elaborated by some authors as (Globerson 1985) (Maskell 1989) (Brown 1996) (Neely et al. 1996) etc. relating to the PIs and the PIS definition process.

These recommendations contain guides and rules for designing Performance Indicators System (PIS). They help in the process of PIS construction by clarifying the limit of performance evaluation measurement, specifying the dimensions/goals and their relations. There are two typologies of frameworks: structural and procedural (Folan and Browne 2005).

A) Structural Frameworks:

These frameworks specify domains, dimensions, and criteria that define the indicators but they do not supply procedures or guidelines that help in the identification and the implementation of these indicators. In other words, these frameworks specify typologies for performance measurement management. The approaches of categories (A) and (D) can be integrated in this category

B) Procedural Frameworks:

These frameworks provide methodologies that offer step-by-step processes for developing performance measures from strategy. These processes are based on general tools that help in the definition and implementation of PIs development. The methods of categories (B) and (C) can be integrated in this category

Classification of existing approaches:

Method Name	Reference	Structural		Procedural	
		(A)	(D)	(B)	(C)
ABC/ABM	(Johnson and Kaplan 1990)	X			
ECOGRAI	(Bitton and Doumeingts 1990)			X	
PMQ (Performance Measurement Questionnaire)	(Dixon et al. 1990)				X
SMART Pyramid	(Lynch and Cross 1991)	X			
BSC (The Balanced Scorecard)	(Azzone et al. 1991)	X			
PBSCW (Putting the Balanced Scorecard to Work)	(Kaplan, R., S and Norton 1993)	X		X	
TOPP System	(Sinteff 1992)	X			X
CPMS (Consistent Performance Measurement System)	(Flapper et al. 1996)			X	

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IDPMS (Integrated Dynamic Performance Measurement System)	(Ghalayini et al. 1997)				X
IPMS (Integrated performance Measurement System)	(Bititci et al. 1997)		X		
AM (Active Monitoring)	(Bititci and Carrie 1998b)	X			X
QMPMS (Quantitative Model for Performance Measurement System)	(Bititci and Carrie 1998a)				X
ENAPS (European Network for Advanced Performance Studies)	(Brown et al. 1998)		X		
IPMF (Integrated Performance Measurement Framework)	(Medori and Steeple 2000)			X	
GIMSI	(Fernandez 2003)			X	
Strategy Map	(Kaplan and Norton 2005)	X			

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MSDP (Measurement System and Development Process)	(Rentes et al. 2002)			X	
DPMS for SME (Dynamic for Performance Measurement System)	(Laitinen 2002)			X	
Ref. Mod for SME (Reference Model for PMM framework and measures)	(Taticchi et al. 2008)			X	
Fuzzy Delphi Method	(Kuo and Chen 2008)			X	

Table 6-1 - Classification of Business Performance Indicators Methods

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6.2 THE ECOGRAI METHOD

While several of the aforementioned methods could in theory be used as a basis for the TOYLABS validation framework, it has been considered important to select a method which has been successfully applied in research and innovation projects and especially in projects related to the manufacturing sector. Based on the literature and the extensive experience of NTUA in the Verification and Validation domain, the ECOGRAI method (Bitton and Doumeingts 1990) has been considered as the most appropriate for TOYLABS. ECOGRAI has been successfully applied in a number of research projects as a basis for validating their results. Its extensive and successful application in the H2020 project FITMAN 'Future Internet Technologies for MANufacturing industries' where ECOGRAI has been adapted and used in order to validate the project results including 10 different large and mid-scale industry use cases in the manufacturing domain, has proved that ECOGRAI is a method which is actually applicable and efficient validating the results of similar actions. Based on the aforementioned fact, ECOGRAI has been selected as the baseline method for the TOYLABS Validation approach. Of course, in order to apply in TOYLABS the ECOGRAI method an adapted version of the basic model has to be built fitting best to the requirements of the project.

ECOGRAI is a method for designing and implementing **Performance Indicator Systems** that can be applied on every production function of an industrial organisation. In this sub-chapter, the ECOGRAI method will be presented and emphasis will be given on its general characteristics and the phases comprising it.

Objective: It seeks to find several customised and limited indicators in agreement with the objectives of decision makers

Main characteristics:

- a logical process of analysis / design using a top-down approach, and allowing to decompose the objectives of the strategic levels into objectives for operational levels
- a concrete process of participative implementation, creating a dialogue between the various levels of the hierarchy, and favouring the identification of indicators by the future users involved in the study : it is a bottom up implementation,
- the use of several tools and graphical supports such as GRAI grids, GRAI nets, splitting up diagrams, coherence panels and specification sheets
- the search of a limited number of Performance Indicators by an original approach that consists of the following steps (Figure 6.1):
 - identification of the objectives assigned to the decision makers

- identification of the variables (Decision Variables or Drivers) on which the decision makers can act to reach their objectives
- identification of the Performance Indicators which measure the efficiency of an activity that aims at reaching one or more of the objectives
- a coherent distribution of Performances Indicators covering the various functions and the various decision levels (strategic / tactical / operational)

Figure 6-1 - The ECOGRAI original approach

The different phases of the method:

The logical structured approach of the method consists of six phases that will be described below:

Figure 6-2 - The six phases of ECOGRAI's structured approach

The first phase includes the modelling of the Production System control structure in order to identify the set of the decision centres, their activities, their links (decisional and informational) and the basic elements which are taken into account to design a Performance Indicator : the objectives and the drivers.

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The second phase includes the identification of the Decision Centre objectives and coherence analysis. A top-down approach is followed, which consists of three steps:

- a) Identifying the objectives of the Production System
- b) Identifying the global objectives of each function belonging to the production process
- c) Defining the objectives of each Decision Centre inside each function

These identifications are based on the notion of contribution: each objective must contribute to the achievement of the objectives identified at an upper level.

The third phase: The identification of the DC Drivers (Decision Variable (DV) or Action Variable (AV)) and analysis of the conflicts. It consists of the drivers' identification corresponding to each objective of the Decision Centres. During the identification of the DV/AV, it is necessary to put in evidence the intra-function and inter-function influences of the Drivers. The aim here is to evaluate the relationships which appear into a function or between functions. Indeed, the proposed objectives (and by consequence the Performance Indicators) for a given Decision Centre are sometimes related to drivers that belong to other Decision Centres. In this case, the degree and origin of the influence should be evaluated.

The fourth phase: Identification of the DC Performance Indicators and internal coherence analysis: it consists of the identification of the Performance Indicators which is validated only by an internal coherence analysis inside each Decision Centre in terms of the triplets {Objectives / Drivers / Performances Indicators}. A triplet is coherent if:

- it is composed of one objective, one or several drivers and one or several performance indicators,
- the performance indicators allow to verify the achievement of the objective, and are influenced by actions on the drivers

Figure 6-3 - Internal Coherence

The fifth phase: Design of the Performance Indicators information system: it consists of the specification of each performance indicator. It is always necessary to define each indicator clearly with fundamental parameters. The tool which guides these definitions is the specification sheet for each indicator which contains:

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- the identification of the indicator (name, decision centre, horizon, period),
- the objectives and the drivers related to the indicator,
- the perverse effects which have been identified,
- the identification of the data required for the implementation of the indicator,
- the definition of the associated processing,
- The way of representing the indicators, determined by the future users.

The sixth phase: Integration of the Performance Indicator information system in the Production information system: this integration is developed using an EIS tool (EIS: Executive Information System) or a Decision Tool. The processing and the visualisation choices that aim at exploiting the Performance Indicators are then specified into the EIS or Decision tool. This work is performed on the specification sheet.

Conclusion on ECOGRAI:

The strengths:

- It proposes generic concepts and generic method to define Performance Indicators in any kind of domain.
- It offers a guideline, a step by step procedure to help the users for its implementation.
- The possibility to use methodological tools (GRAI grid, coherence table) in order to determine the various elements needed for PIS design.
- The link established between the three basic concepts: Objective, Decision Variable (DV) or Action Variable (AV), Performance Indicators.
- Its top-down approach for the deployment of objectives and the bottom-up for the aggregation of the performance indicators.
- It is compatible with the use of any generic objectives and performance indicators defined in other methods.

Strength and originality:

The main advantage of ECOGRAI is that it limits the number of Performance Indicators. Usually the Performance Indicators are defined directly from the objectives (arrow number 2 on figure 6.4). The result is a large number of PI. In these kinds of situations, it is difficult to follow all the PIs and even more to determine which DV or AV must be activated to improve the situation. In ECOGRAI, the starting point is the search of DV or AV to reach the objectives (Arrow 1 between

Objectives and DA). Afterwards, the PIs characterise the result of DV or AV in reaching the objectives (arrow 1 between PI and DV or AV).

In such a situation, it is possible to determine rapidly where it is necessary to act in order to improve it.

Figure 6-4: Principle of ECOGRAI

The weakness:

- The obligation to customize the method to the chosen domain.

This can take some time but later, it is possible to reuse the customized method for all the use cases in the same domain

It can be concluded from the above that the ECOGRAI framework is a great tool on which the ToyLabs' Validation method can be based. As a result, the next chapter will be responsible for modifying the ECOGRAI method (by subtracting some of the phases) in such a way that it can be later used under the scope of ToyLabs in order to define the criteria and Key Performance Indicators necessary for evaluating the platform's impact.

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7 BUSINESS PERFORMANCE INDICATORS FOR TOYLABS

7.1 A SIMPLIFIED VERSION OF ECOGRAI

For the ToyLabs application, a simplified version of ECOGRAI will be used, since the project is relatively small in duration and as a result, the method used for performance measurement should be simpler and less time consuming to implement. As a result, a modified version of ECOGRAI will be described, with only three phases distilled from the ECOGRAI method in order to facilitate the application, and to adapt to the size of the trials and the duration of the project.

First Phase: Description of the system in which the performance indicators will be defined.

It is impossible to define correct Performance Indicators (PIs) for any kinds of activities, if the conditions in which these activities are performed are unknown. Thus, it is necessary to describe the elements, functions, processes etc. of the system where these PIs will be determined.

For that reason, System Modeling will be used. For the description of a system using System Modeling the following need to be determined:

- The elements that compose the system and the relations between these elements.
- The functions that allow the achievement of the objectives.
- The processes that support the dynamic transformations.
- The boundary that delimits the elements not belonging to the system. It could be interesting to evaluate the influence of these external elements on the developed system. It is generally recommended listing only the elements outside of the system.
- The dynamic of evolution of the system, particularly in the case of evolution from “AS IS” to “TO BE”. In fact, a system is always evolving, otherwise it dies. The speed of evolution can be low or rapid.
- The objectives assigned to the system.

Second Phase: According to the objectives of the system, the owner determines the potential actions in order to reach these objectives (called Decision Variables (DV) or Action Variables (AV)).

The **Third Phase** is responsible for defining the performance indicators that characterize the reaching of the objectives by using the DV/AV.

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7.2 ECOGRAI TO TOYLABS

Phase 1- Description of the system:

Elements of the System:

- 1) Stakeholders
 - a. Visitor
 - b. Certified User
 - c. Manufacturer
 - d. FabLabs
 - e. Safety/Environmental/Childhood Expert
 - f. End User
- 2) Platform Components/Modules
 - a. ToyLabs Platform
 - b. Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component
 - c. Partner Matching Module
 - d. Augmented Reality Module

Functions and Processes

- New product development in the toy industry based on the pillars of co-creation and open innovation
 - Procedure of Immersion/Conceptualisation for a new idea/concept
 - Design of a new product
 - Prototype Manufacturing
 - Production of the final product
 - Commercialisation of the final product

Dynamic Evolution of the System

- A web platform will be developed that will offer the capability to develop a new product from the stages of Immersion & Concept Definition up to the stage of Commercialisation. The platform will rely heavily on the pillars of collaboration between all the stakeholders who will provide feedback and valuable insights to the process.

Boundary of the system

- The external stakeholders (partners, customers, etc.). In other words, the stakeholders that lie outside of the system's boundary are those that do not participate in any way in the platform's procedures for new product development and are also not active in the platform's other functionalities such as liking projects, giving feedback etc. It is difficult to assess how these stakeholders

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affect the system and its effectiveness. However, if a manufacturer that uses the platform notices a rise in his customers, which means that the external stakeholders react to the improved quality/imagination of products produced with the help of the ToyLabs platform.

Objectives of TOYLABS

1. Manufacturer Objectives
 - a. Increased quality of final product
 - b. Reduction of issues related to the various stages of new product development
 - c. Increased opportunities for quality collaboration relationships
 - d. Reduction of time/cost for the design of a new product
 - e. Reduction of problems related to the design of a new product (design details, safety issues etc.) by receiving early feedback from collaborating organisations
 - f. Reduction of time/cost for prototype manufacturing
 - g. Increased quality of constructed prototype
 - h. New channels for commercialization purposes
 - i. Protection of Intellectual Property Rights
 - j. Better organisational tools for improving the toy development process (i.e. feasibility study)
2. FabLabs Objectives
 - a. Expand their customer network
 - b. Increase their potential collaboration opportunities regardless of geographical barriers
3. Expert Objectives
 - a. Expand their customer network
 - b. Increase their potential collaboration opportunities regardless of geographical barriers
 - c. Expand their range of services by participating to more stages of new product development
4. End-User Objectives
 - a. Have a meaningful participation in the toy development process
 - b. Receive incentives/prizes for participating
 - c. Be able to post ideas and comments for products

Phase 2: Definition of AV/DV, constraints and criteria:

AV/DV:

- To implement the ToyLabs platform in new product development
- To adopt the technologies related to the platform's basic modules

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Criteria:

- Quality
- Time
- Cost
- Safety
- Collaboration

Phase 3: Determination of Performance Indicators

#	Performance Indicator	Description	Related Stakeholders
1	Time-to-market	Lead time between the idea of the new product and the date of commercialization to the customer	Manufacturer
1.1	Market analysis time	Time it takes to perform a market analysis for a specific concept/idea using the platform's functionalities	Manufacturer
1.2	Time to design new product	Lead time between the start of the Design stage and the date of completion	Manufacturer
1.3	Time to construct the prototype	Lead time between the start of the Prototyping stage and the date of completion	Manufacturer
1.4	Time to find a collaborator	Lead time between a member of the platform realizing he has need of a partner and him finding the right partner	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts
1.5	Inquiry/feedback response time	Lead time between a partner asking for an inquiry/feedback and the response by the	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts

		partner to whom the inquiry was intended	
1.6	Time for data exchange	Time it takes for a partner to download/receive the necessary data for a specific project	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts
1.7	Number of iterations in the quoting process	Number of cycles between the stakeholders to achieve the final version of the quotation	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts
2	Cost for new product development	Cost for the entire process of new product development	Manufacturer
2.1	Market Analysis cost	Cost for performing market analysis	Manufacturer
2.2	Design cost	Cost for designing a new product	Manufacturer
2.3	Prototype cost	Cost for constructing the prototype	Manufacturer
2.4	Operation margin	Reduction in the cost of the project management, by allowing remote participation	Manufacturer
3	Quality of the entire process	Overall quality of the final product and its intermediary stages as well as overall quality of the platform's services	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts, End-Users
3.1	Number of issues	Number of issues/problems that appear throughout the whole process	Manufacturer

3.2	Average rating of the ToyLabs Platform	Average rating of the platform that is carried out through the platform's rating system	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts, End-Users
3.3	Accuracy of feasibility study	Relative difference between the actual and planned cost/time for development	Manufacturer
3.4	FabLabs Quality of Service	Mean rating of FabLabs that participate in the platform	FabLabs
3.5	Experts Quality of Service	Mean rating of experts that participate in the platform	Experts
4	Safety Levels	Number of safety standards performed on the design/ prototype/ product	Manufacturer
5	Level of participation of stakeholders (apart from the manufacturer)	Mean number of partners/new product development process	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts, End-Users
5.1	Number of ideas	Number of ideas posted by customers for new products	End Users
5.2	Number of comments on toys	Number of comments when a manufacturer turns the visibility of a product on and asks for feedback	Manufacturer
5.3	Number of stakeholders answering a request	Number of people/organisations that answer a manufacturer's call for collaboration	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts

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5.4	Number of new collaborations	Number of clients that a FabLab/expert receives through the platform	FabLab, Experts
5.5	Number of services partner	Number of services performed by a partner throughout a product development process	Manufacturer, FabLabs, Experts

Table 7-1 - ToyLabs Key Performance Indicators

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8 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

Figure 8-1 - ToyLabs Co-Creation & Open Innovation Methodology

In Part B of the present deliverable the project's validation framework has been defined by drawing information from the bibliographic research performed. Special attention was given to the ECOGRAI methodology which is widely used for defining performance indicators in relevant cases. ECOGRAI works by seeking to find a number of customized and limited indicators in agreement with the objectives of the project's decision makers. ECOGRAI is an extensive framework which requires a flexible adoption of its phases per project.

Consequently, by selecting the ECOGRAI's phases which fit to TOYLABS, an adopted method of ECOGRAI has been defined which includes the following steps:

1. Defining the elements, functions, processes etc. of the platform
2. Defining the objectives of the platform's stakeholders
3. Defining the Action/Decision Variables and criteria for validation
4. Defining the Key Performance Indicators that will measure the platform's success in reaching the objectives of step 2.

In the second iteration of the present deliverable, the above-mentioned performance indicators will be analysed further and given quantifiable goals so that

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they can be used in the later stages of the project to measure ToyLabs' impact in dealing with the challenges that SMEs in EU's toy industry are facing today.

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ANNEX I: QUESTIONNAIRES

Questionnaire for Toy Industry Representatives

The purpose of this questionnaire is to gather information about the processes and techniques in toy manufacturing, not to evaluate you; so remember that there are no right or wrong answers, we simply want to know your opinion.

General questions

QXX. Please indicate your profile (multiple choice)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Design
<input type="checkbox"/>	Engineering/ technical office
<input type="checkbox"/>	Quality control
<input type="checkbox"/>	R&D
<input type="checkbox"/>	Test laboratory technician
<input type="checkbox"/>	Production / Operations
<input type="checkbox"/>	Logistics
<input type="checkbox"/>	Manager / Director
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commercial / Sales
<input type="checkbox"/>	Marketing
<input type="checkbox"/>	Finance and administration
<input type="checkbox"/>	Other (please specify)

QXX. Please indicate the name of the organisation where you work

QXX. Select the country where you work (multiple choice)

QXX. Select the country where your company carries out product design (multiple choice)

QXX. Select the country where your company manufactures (multiple choice)

QXX. Please confirm that you work in the toy sector

	Yes, I work in or for the toy sector
	No, I neither work in nor for the toy sector (<i>questionnaire ends*</i>)

*Thank you for your interest in collaborating through this questionnaire. Unfortunately, we are focusing on gathering information about the toy sector.

QXX. Please indicate the category of products manufactured by your company. If your company manufactures more than three categories, please select those three with the highest number of units produced

	Activity toys (swings, slides, gym set, etc.)
	Aquatic toys (inflatable PVC toys, bathing toys, etc.)
	Arts and crafts materials and related articles (crayons, chinks, pens, scissors, etc.)
	Audio/visual equipment (music boxes, simple computers, CD players, etc.)
	Books with play value
	Construction toys and puzzles
	Costumes, disguises and masks (intended to imitate)
	Dolls and soft-filled toys
	Experimental sets (electrical, photographic sets, etc.)
	Functional toys (toolboxes, microscopes, typewriters, etc.)
	Game sets (picture dominoes, simple matching games, board games, bingo, etc.)
	Mechanical and/or electrical driven vehicles (not intended to bear the mass of a child: trains that make noise, pull-back vehicles, track racing sets, action figure vehicles, etc.)
	Play scenes and constructed models (farms, garages, dollhouses, detailed and realistic cars, puppet theatres, etc.)
	Projectile toys with launching device (toys that eject balls, bows and arrows, etc.)
	Push-along toys and walking aids (animals on wheels, boats, cars, etc.)

	Role-playing toys (for imitation of adult activities: toy telephones, play dishes and tea sets, doll shopping carts, etc.)
	Sand-water toys (sand tools with simple shapes, watering cans, plastic cars/vans, radio-controlled boats/ships, etc.)
	Skill development toys (stacking blocks, shape sorters, sewing kits, modelling sets, etc.)
	Toy cosmetics
	Toy musical instruments
	Toy sports equipment and balls
	Toys for babies to look at, grasping and/or squeezing (activity centres, teething rings, cribs and play gyms, etc.)
	Toys intended to bear the mass of a child (toy scooters, rocking horses, pedal cars, etc.)
	Toys intended to be entered by a child (soft houses or tents, rigid playhouses, play tunnels, etc.)
	Other (please specify)

//// TOY CATEGORY 1: NAME ////

Repeat this section for a maximum of three categories

QXX. Which kind of raw materials do you use in your products in the selected categories (not including packaging)? (multiple choice)

<input type="checkbox"/>	Plastics, additives, resins
<input type="checkbox"/>	Wood and derivatives
<input type="checkbox"/>	Metal
<input type="checkbox"/>	Textile
<input type="checkbox"/>	Paper and cardboard
<input type="checkbox"/>	Others (please specify)

QXX. Please indicate the activity you perform in you company when producing the products in the categories selected (multiple choice)

	I produce the raw materials and/or components to manufacture the product
	I transform and define the raw materials and/or components to manufacture the product
	I apply finishing to the manufactured product
	Others (please specify)

PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND RESINS

QXX. Please indicate whether you elaborate raw material and/or components based on PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND RESINS

	Yes
	No

QXX. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND RESINS

	Injection moulding
	Extrusion
	Blow moulding
	Rotational moulding
	Additive manufacturing / 3D printing
	Thermoforming
	Laminating
	Machining
	Others (please specify)

QXX. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding PLASTICS, ADDITIVES AND RESINS

	Deburring
	Painting
	Coating
	Adhesion
	Polishing
	Machining / Milling
	Others (please specify)

WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

QXX. Please indicate whether you elaborate raw material and/or components based on WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

	Yes
	No

QXX. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

	Sawing
	Debarking
	Drying in a chamber
	Brushing
	Chipping or similar
	Sheet metal cutting
	Sheet wood cutting
	Pressing operations
	Edge banding
	Drilling

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	Milling
	Turning
	Others (please specify)

QXX. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding WOOD AND DERIVATIVES

	Sanding
	Cleaning operations
	Varnishing
	Milling
	Others (please specify)

METAL

QXX. Please indicate whether you elaborate raw material and/or components based on METAL

	Yes
	No

QXX. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding METAL

	Additive manufacturing
	Melting
	Welding and joining technologies
	Powder metallurgy
	Machining
	Conformation (stamping, bending of the sheets)

	Surface and thermal treatments
	Sheet metal cutting (laser, water jet cutter)
	Punching
	Injection
	Soldering
	Metal casting
	Sand casting
	Cold lamination
	Cold extrusion
	Drilling
	Milling
	Turning
	Others (please specify)

QXX. Please indicate finishing processes used in your company regarding METAL

	Polishing
	Chip finishing
	Abrasive grinding
	Grinding
	Lapping
	Knurling
	Burnishing
	Chemical and electrochemical processes

	Sandblasting
	Reaming
	Electrolytic coatings
	Anneal
	Galvanize
	Anodized
	Chrome plating
	Others (please specify)

TEXTILES

QXX. Please indicate whether you elaborate raw material and/or components based on TEXTILES

	Yes
	No

QXX. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding TEXTILES

	Cutting
	Sewing
	Yarn or spinning
	Fibre production
	Weaving
	Tailoring
	High frequency soldering

	Others (please specify)
--	-------------------------

QXX. Please indicate finishing processes used in your company regarding TEXTILES

	Stamping
	Dyeing
	Stiffening
	Bleaching
	Calendering
	Printing
	Others (please specify)

PAPER AND CARDBOARD

QXX. Please indicate whether you elaborate raw material and/or components based on PAPER AND CARDBOARD

	Yes
	No

QXX. Please indicate the manufacturing processes used in your company regarding PAPER AND CARDBOARD

	Pressing
	Drying
	Calendering
	Cutting and winding

	Others (please specify)
--	-------------------------

QXX. Please indicate the finishing processes used in your company regarding PAPER AND CARDBOARD

	Satin
	Coated
	Handled
	Processed
	Bound
	Folded
	Perforated
	Varnished
	Laminated
	Others (please specify)

QXX. What do you think the production technologies of toys will be in the next five years?

--

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//// TOY CATEGORY n: NAME ////
If respondent selects more than 1 product category, the previous block is replicated as many times as toy categories have been selected

FAB LABS AND TOY LABS

A Fab Lab (fabrication laboratory) is a small-scale workshop offering – personalised– [digital fabrication](#). It is equipped with machines and technologies that cover several different length scales and various materials. They can be used in all phases of product development and, therefore, allow the client or user to perform as much of the product development as possible in the Fab Lab.

There are several official Fab Labs around the world, providing access to the tools and knowledge to educate, innovate and develop the use of technology and digital manufacturing to enable anyone to do “almost everything”, creating opportunities to innovate.

<input type="checkbox"/>	OK, I understand
--------------------------	------------------

QXX. Do you currently use services or technologies offered by Fab Labs?

<input type="checkbox"/>	Yes
<input type="checkbox"/>	No (<i>skip to Q.XX</i>)
<input type="checkbox"/>	I do not know

QXX. Indicate the Fab Lab technologies that you are currently using in your company (multiple choice)

<input type="checkbox"/>	3D printing
<input type="checkbox"/>	3D scanning
<input type="checkbox"/>	Acrylic bending machine
<input type="checkbox"/>	Circuit production
<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC milling
<input type="checkbox"/>	Drone
<input type="checkbox"/>	Furnace
<input type="checkbox"/>	Hot string

	Knitting machine
	Laser cutting
	Lathing
	Pottery wheel infrared oven
	Precision milling
	Sandblasting
	Sewing machine
	Soldering station
	Thermostatic basin
	Transfer press
	Vacuum forming
	Vinyl cutting
	Virtual reality
	Welding machine
	None
	I do not know which technologies my company is using
	Others (please specify)

QXX. Now you have indicated the technologies you are using, please indicate the services that your company is currently using in the Fab Labs

	Studies with users and knowledge about the target of the product
	Trend and social analysis
	Consultancy regarding technology application
	Consultancy regarding manufacturing processes
	Consultancy regarding materials

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	Certification
	Others (please specify)
	None
	My company does not use any services from Fab Labs
	I do not know if my company uses services from Fab Labs

The idea of a Toy Lab is focused on creating a Fab Lab specialised in the toy industry, creating a multi-stakeholder network where key players in the toy industry value network (i.e., toy manufacturers, FabLabs, Toy Safety experts, childhood professionals, end customers, etc.) are brought together and collaborate closely in order to come up with new, innovative toys and games.

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QXX. Please indicate which services would be of most interest for your company (multiple choice)

	Studies with users and knowledge about the target of the product
	Trend and social analysis
	Consultancy regarding technology application
	Consultancy regarding manufacturing processes
	Consultancy regarding materials
	Certification
	Others (please specify)
	None
	My company does not use any services from Fab Labs
	I do not know if my company uses services from Fab Labs

QXX. If there was an ideal Toy Lab, the services of most interest to my company would be focused on...

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Thank you very much for participating in this questionnaire. Your answers will be of great assistance in developing the ToyLabs European project.

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Questionnaires for ToyLabs Partners

Manufacturers

Q1:	Please provide a short description of your company's profile
<p><i>About 1-2 paragraphs...</i></p>	

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Q2:	Do you have a standard process for new product development? Please explain this process from the stage of ideation and conceptualisation of a new product up to its production (including concept definition, product design, safety assessment, prototyping etc.)
------------	---

Free text (including any useful images and figures)

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Q3:	Is every stage of your process carried out in the same country/location?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q4:	What problems do you usually run into during the toy creation process? Is there a standard way of solving them? Are there any recurring problems that you would wish to solve?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q5:	Do you collaborate with safety experts? At which steps of the production process and how do you exchange material?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q6:	Do you do prototyping yourselves or do you use external collaborators? If yes, how do you collaborate and exchange information/data?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q7:	What kinds of information/data do you exchange with any of your external collaborators (for prototyping, for safety assessment or for any other activities)?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q8:	Do you collect feedback from childhood experts or customers and if yes, how?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q9:	Do you use any technical platforms/IT systems today and for what reason?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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FabLabs & Experts

Q1:	Please provide a short description of your profile and your main activities.
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About 1-2 paragraphs...

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Q2:	Could you describe the services you provide to toy manufacturers?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q3:	On which lifecycle phases of the toy manufacturing process do you engage yourselves (design, prototyping, testing etc.)?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q4:	Do you collect feedback from potential customers or experts and if yes, what is the exact process you follow?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	

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Q5:	What kinds of information/data do you exchange with your clients or external collaborators? Could you provide some examples and/or any sample of the information you exchange?
<i>Free text (including any useful images and figures)</i>	